

**Development of MXene-MOF
synergized electrode materials for
efficient energy storage applications**

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of the University of the West of Scotland
for the award of Doctor of Philosophy

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Declaration

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Publication list

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- **M. Adil**, Abdul Ghani Olabi, Mohammad Ali Abdelkareem, Hussain Alawadhi, Ahmed Bahaa, Khaled ElSaid, C. Rodriguez, In-situ grown Fe MOF-MXene composite for solid state asymmetric supercapacitors (To be published)
- A review on In-situ grown MXene-MOFs synergized electrodes for efficient supercapacitors recent advancements and future work (Expected publication)

Nomenclature

ASC	Asymmetric supercapacitor
AC	Activated Carbon
C_{sc}	Specific capacity (mAh/g)
C_{AC}	Areal capacity (mAh/cm ²)
C_{Vc}	Volumetric capacity (mAh/cm ³)
CNT	Carbon nanotube
CoS	Cobalt sulfide
FeCu	Iron Copper
E	Energy density (Wh/kg)
EDLC	Electric double-layer capacitor
EDS	Energy dispersive spectroscopy
EIS	Electrochemical impedance spectroscopy
FE-SEM	Field emission scanning electron microscopy
GCD	Galvanostatic charge-discharge measurements
GO	Graphene oxide
HR-TEM	High-resolution transmission electron microscopy
NF	Nickle foam
I	Current density
XPS	X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy
1D	One-dimensional
ESR	Equivalent Series Resistance
R_{ct}	Charge transfer resistance
PVDF	Polyvinylidene difluoride
Pt	Platinum
P	Power density (W/kg)
NP	Nanoparticles
MCs	Metal chalcogenides
LIBs	Lithium-ion battery
SC	Supercapacitors
SAED	Selected area electron diffraction

XRD	X-ray diffraction
3D	Three-dimensional
2D	Two-dimensional
S	Sulfur
Rs	Internal/ solution resistance (Ω)
CV	Cyclic voltammetry
SS	Solid State
EC	Electrochemistry
MOF	Metal Organic Framework

Abstract

Conventionally supercapacitors (SCs) tend to possess high power density and low energy density, whereas batteries have high energy density but low power density. Therefore, it is imperative to design SC electrodes with energy density comparable to batteries if not equal, while maintaining their characteristic high values of power density. The goal is to shrink the gap between SCs and batteries, as well as improvement in capacity retention is also of vital. It is therefore very important to study and evaluate new composite materials that have not been studied much. Identification of relevant material, synthesis route and stability of the active materials are the key questions that need to be thoroughly addressed. MXene (2D titanium carbide) is widely studied in recent time for a variety of applications. This family of 2d materials offers tremendous properties such as hydrophilicity, metallic conductivity as well as high redox activity when employed in energy storage applications. However, MXene possess excellent electrochemical properties, yet there are some structural defects such as restacking and sheet crushing that limit their stability which is of paramount importance for an energy storage device. Material design that could prevent the sheets from restacking and cease the process of sheet crushing is very important. It is therefore concluded that if gaps between MXene sheets should be filled with an appropriate material that could fit in the spacing between the flakes without harming the nature of actual material. Metal organic frameworks (MOFs) a class of highly crystalline materials, with porous structure and large surface area which is widely studied for SCs applications. Pristine MOFs suffer from compromised values of specific capacities and rate capability when used as electrode therefor using them in a composite form for electrochemical applications is preferable. Herein, a relatively novel strategy is proposed to design composite material between MXene, MOFs and MOF derived structures. It is also worth mentioning that synthesis strategy proposed here involves no external binder instead all the active materials are directly grown in an in-situ growth method on the substrate to achieve a direct electrode growth. MOFs and MXene flakes are blended, in a hydrothermal synthesis route and subsequently grown over the Ni foam (NF). This way ion/electron diffusion pathways could be shortened, and electroactive sites could be enhanced. Consequently, MXene flakes were prevented from restacking that improved overall stability of the composite, whereas high crystallinity and surface area of MOFs helped in overall improvement of rich active sites. Three different electrode materials and devices were fabricated and assembled. MXene-CoS, MXene-FeCu MOF and MXene-Fe MOF were individually tested in three electrode system as well as assembled in a two electrode supercapacitor device. As prepared electrodes and devices manifested excellent rate capability and cyclic performances. Moreover, all the electrodes showed superb values of energy and power density that are crucial to evaluate the performance of any energy storage device. The proposed method offers a generic protocol to design and fabricate MXene-MOF synergized composite with excellent electrochemical energy storage properties as well as extraordinary cyclic stability. Moreover, this study also offers an endless potential to be explored for future electrochemical energy storage devices especially for commercial purposes.

Chapter 1. Introduction

1.1 Introduction

Fossil fuels remained a key source of energy supply for long time. The vigorous exploitation has gravely exhausted these reserves and are expected to deplete in decades to come. Moreover, extensive exploration and massive utilization of fossil fuels poses a severe threat to the environment therefore need for cleaner and greener energy resources has increased exponentially (Obaideen et al., 2022). Electrochemical (EC) energy storage devices primarily supercapacitors (SCs) and batteries have been pivotal in energy storage research and development (Bahaa et al., 2019). The reliance on these storage devices is so high that everyday life can come to stand still in the absence of these devices. These devices are the major source of energy for our cellular phones, computers, electric vehicles (EV) etc. Batteries are electrochemical devices that manifest high energy density, but they offer lower values of power density (Simon et al., 2014). Batteries such as metal ion batteries, flow batteries etc are among widely used and studied batteries (Abassi et al., 2021).

On the other hand, SCs offer quick charging and discharging cycles with high power density and specific capacity (Adil et al., 2021) . The history, mechanism, and types of SCs have been thoroughly discussed in chapter 2. Since SCs suffer from lower values of energy density, therefore desire to achieve such devices that offer high values of both energy and power densities becomes relevant. Pseudocapacitors are the type of SCs that offer energy density comparable to that of batteries while possessing high value of power density (Brousse et al., 2015). Based on their electrochemical properties SCs have been used as memory backup in a variety of consumer-based

applications such as microcomputers, clocks, system boards etc. Along with that SCs are also used in roadside warning lights, solar watches, and solar lanterns (Adil et al., 2021). With the advancements in SCs, they are also employed as short time energy storage resources in EVs, vehicles powered by fuel cells, emergency power sources for hospitals and eclectic systems at other public places. However, pseudocapacitors have merits over contemporary conventional SCs yet at the same time there are some shortcomings associated with them such as compromised cyclic stability and low conductivity. Therefore, it is imperative to design and fabricate, more efficient pseudocapacitive electrodes with longer cyclic stability, high conductivity while maintaining high values of energy and power densities.

Two dimensional (2D) materials have been widely studied as electrode material in various energy storage applications. Graphene has been a dominant 2D layered material used in electrochemical storage devices (R. Kumar et al., 2022). Despite that, graphene has been an excellent material, but there are certain challenges associated that need to be addressed. One of the key challenges is its manufacturing cost as well as delicate synthesis procedure (N. Kumar et al., 2021). Therefore, need for research and development of 2D materials with similar properties, simpler synthesis route, cheaper production cost and commercial scalability has emerged.

MXene, a relatively new and emerging family of 2D layered materials composed of transition metal based either carbides, nitrides or carbonitrides first came in limelight in 2011 discovered by researchers from Drexel University (Naguib, Kurtoglu, et al., 2011). MXene sheets are obtained from the exfoliation of MAX phases, here M is for transition metals, A is for elements from group III and IV whereas X is for carbide and nitride content (Garg et al., 2020a). A detailed discussion on structure, properties, synthesis, and applications of MXene is carried out in chapter 2. So far more than 30

types of MXene have been reported, among them ($\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{T}_x$) MXene widely investigated for a vast spectrum of applications (J. Luo et al., 2020). Excellent redox chemistry, metallic conductivity and hydrophilicity are the distinct features of ($\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{T}_x$) MXene which make them excellent candidate for electrode material for electrochemical energy storage applications (Ramachandran, Rajavel, et al., 2018). Numerous studies have been reported where stand-alone MXene and its composites have been reported for SC applications, such as MXene-hole graphene, polymerized MXene (V_2C), Ni-MXene, Zn-MXene composite. A wide range of Transition metal oxides (TMOs) composites with MXene have also been reported such as MnO_2 , NiO, MoO_3 , WO_3 , Fe_2O_3 etc (Adil et al., 2023). Despite these superior properties there are some key challenges involved such as restacking and re-crushing of MXene sheet which significantly limit their performance (Zang et al., 2020). Therefore, it is important to fabricate such composites that could prevent restacking and crushing of MXene sheets and shorten the ion diffusion pathways.

MOFs a category of porous materials composed of metal ions or clusters interlinked by organic ligands. Therefore, the following structures are greatly ordered, crystalline, and have an exceptionally large surface area, these properties make their utilization in a large sphere of applications that covers gas storage, sensing devices, separation, as well as catalysis. High surface area, structural tunability of pore size, together with high thermal and chemical stability have brought them immense attraction specifically in the field of energy storage and particularly in SCs. Owing to such incredible properties, MOFs tend to be one of the ideal materials in storing electrical energy in the form of electrochemical charge separation. To date thousands of MOFs structures have been developed with distinct properties and potential applications. Compromised electrical conductivity, is among the major obstacles that MOFs suffer in SCs

applications. Hence designing MOFs with high electrical conductivity is imperative. However, recent advancements in tailoring the design and MOFs synthesis have led to achieve more conductive MOFs and making them propitious electrode materials for energy storage applications. Overall, MOFs depict exceptional ability to be used in energy storage and SCs applications, and ongoing research is likely to uncover even more applications of these materials in the domain of energy storage.

Using pristine MOFs in SC can further be divided in to two classes, such as direct application of pristine MOFs as electrode and using MOFs structures as templates for metal oxides, mixed metal oxides, metal nanoparticles and porous carbon structures (J. Yang et al., 2017). Calcination is the procedure that abolishes pristine MOF structures, crushes molecular active sites, and leads to below par specific surface area hence external agents or molecules are inducted to reduce defects and enhance stability (Balamurugan et al., 2017; Y. Sun et al., 2017).

Keeping above mentioned limitations in account, it is important to use MOFs in a composite formation with an appropriate material so that these structural limitations could be overcome, and efficient SC device could be actualized. Herein a new study is being proposed to synergies MXene and MOFs structures so that the merits of both materials could be fully utilized, and shortcomings could be overcome by benefiting the advantages of both materials offer over each other. Such as, reduced electrical conductivity of MOFs can be strengthened by introducing MXene, whereas the interspacing between MXene flakes could be infused by MOFs which will help in shortening the diffusion pathways as well as further enhance the surface area along with improved active sites.

1.2 Novelty

In this study, simple and cost effective synthesis route is adopted to actualize a composite that could possess excellent electrochemical properties. Therefore, three different electrodes were fabricated such as MXene-CoS, MXene-FeCu MOF and MXene-Fe MOF to carry out three different studies. Moreover, no external entity or binder was used to paste active material on the substrate NF, which helps a stronger adhesion between active material and NF. To our best information, these composites have not been prepared using in situ grown method, therefore have never been used in SC applications. In MXene-CoS, MOF derived CoS is made composite with MXene and directly grown on NF to obtain composite material. Whereas MXene-FeCu MOF composite material was developed in a similar manner and in this composite a bimetallic MOF was prepared and incorporated with MXene. Lastly, MXene-Fe MOF electrode was prepared. The prepared electrodes were electrochemically tested and have given excellent pseudocapacitive results, making them promising electrodes for future work.

1.3 Aims and Objectives

The aim of this study is to conceptualize a composite material, that can give extraordinary SC performance. The aim is to carry out an in-depth study on SCs, that could bridge the performance gap between SCs and batteries by developing efficient and novel materials. The identification of structural shortcomings and chemical limitations of MOFs and MXene are aimed. Moreover, it is also aimed to benefit from the merits of both constituents and capping the structural limitations by making a new composite. Another important aspect of this work is to achieve high purity and excellent morphology of the materials. Consequently, efficient and stable electrodes and devices to be made that could set a strong base for future work. Moreover, it is also aimed that this work should be potentially viable for commercial expansion.

The objective of this study is to achieve in-situ growth of MXene-MOF synergized materials with Pseudocapacitive/battery-type characteristics. After the synthesis of the composite, the obtained product to be grown on the NF in a binder free growth mechanism. Since shrinking the performance gap between SCs and batteries is aimed, therefore the developed pseudocapacitive electrodes are supposed to have high energy density while maintaining their characteristic high power density. The electrochemical performance is to be evaluated for each electrode in a three electrode configuration, as well as in a two electrode asymmetric supercapacitor (ASC) device.

Discussion

The scope of this study is to carry-out a detailed investigation of this relatively novel composite and offer a great potential of investigating different MOFs and MXene composites for the future work. Since MXene is synergized with three different MOFs and derived materials. Therefore, if more MOFs are to be composited with MXene this will give diverse knowledge of overall potential of these composites. The successful conclusion of this work will set a strong foundation for new SCs materials with a great potential to be scaled up for commercial use.

Chapter 2. Literature Review

In this chapter a thorough discussion is carried out on various aspects of the desired work. Historical background of SCs, their types working and commonly used active materials are described in detail. A brief and comprehensive discussion on electrolyte is also undertaken. Active materials such as MXene and MOFs have been profoundly explained in the second part of this chapter. Background, chemical composition, synthesis routes, precursors, physical and chemical properties etc all of them are deeply studied. Later on, MXene-MOF composite is reasoned well, its merits and limitations are comprehensively explained.

2.1 Historical Background

Electrochemical SCs predominantly known as Supercapacitors have been extensively studied in recent decades (Kötz & Carlen, 2000). However, the real evolution of Electric double layered capacitors (EDLC) was carried out after middle of 20th century. Which is long after since the initial idea of double-layer capacitors was floated in 1853 by Herman von Helmholtz. SCs offer electrochemical energy storage system with longer cycling life higher power density and reversibility. It was 1950's when electrochemical capacitor with porous carbon structure was employed as an electrode material. Standard Oil Company, Cleveland, Ohio (SOHIO) patented another energy storage device in 1962 where it was recognized that the double layered interfaces behave like capacitors of relatively high specific capacity (Miller & Burke, 2008). In 1971 Nippon Electric Company (NEC) was the first company to produce double-layer capacitors and named as "supercapacitors" (Endo et al., 2001). Henceforth, a wide spectrum of studies was opened to improve electrode and electrolyte materials as well as manufacturing procedure. Currently, SCs are being employed for a vast spectrum

of applications like hybrid vehicles, laser techniques, electronic devices, computer UPSs, memory devices and energy storage for solar cells (Sharma & Bhatti, 2010).

2.2 General overview of Batteries and Supercapacitors

Electrochemical measurements are the fundamental tools to distinguish between electrical energy storage devices either a battery or a supercapacitor. Energy density is the measurement of amount of energy that can be stored in a device per unit weight. Whereas power density tells the rate of energy per unit weight of the obtained from the device (Sahay & Dwivedi, 2009). Batteries offer slow charging and discharging process whereas supercapacitors offer quick and longer cycles of charging and discharging. Supercapacitors offer high power density but limited energy density in contrast batteries offer high energy density but less power density (Gogotsi & Simon, 2011; Q. Jiang et al., 2018; Simon et al., 2014). It is electrochemical process that distinguishes between a supercapacitor and a battery. Supercapacitors have relatively simple operating and construction mechanism compared to batteries. Cheap and sustainable electrode materials like porous carbon and aqueous electrolytes such as Li_2SO_4 or KOH can be used for the development of SCs. Hybrid batteries a new class of energy storage device that combines both batteries and supercapacitors to be employed as hybrid energy storage device.

The charge storage process in SCs involves adsorption as well as absorption of ions during the electrode and electrolyte interaction, that leads to charge storage. Whereas in batteries redox reactions occur that cause metal ions insertion in the electrode materials (Q. Jiang et al., 2018). On the other hand, pseudocapacitive materials not only provide active sites for battery-type redox reactions but also exhibit capacitor-like features. Such features enable these materials to store high energy density as that of battery materials with the capacity of exhibiting charge/discharge cycles within the

same time interval of capacitive materials (Y. Jiang & Liu, 2019). Although Battery-type and pseudocapacitive materials both are redox active, however, distinct charge storing behavior of pseudocapacitive materials considerably enhance their performance. The dominant charge storing mechanisms in pseudocapacitive materials can be listed as: (i) redox reactions occurring in the vicinity of electrode surface, and (ii) intercalated ions into layered materials via quick conducting channels (C. Choi et al., 2020). These mechanisms are independent of sluggish kinetics due to solid-state ion diffusion as well as phase changes behavior of intercalated compounds. Pseudocapacitive materials were first proposed by Conway in 1962 due to absorbed hydrogen at the surface of metal electrode which was categorized into adsorption, surface redox, and intercalation in terms of charge storing mechanism (Bhojane, 2022). Moreover, adsorption pseudocapacitance is usually referred as underpotential deposition (UPD), seldomly involved in electrochemical energy storage devices (Y. Liu, Jiang, et al., 2020).

2.3 Working Principle of capacitors and supercapacitors

Capacitor is one of the fundamental devices to be used in any electrical circuits. Supercapacitors have their own merits over conventional capacitors, such as SCs offer higher capacity than capacitors.

2.3.1 Working Principle of conventional capacitors

A conventional capacitor consists of a set of two conducting plates also called electrodes. These electrodes are set apart by an insulating material called dielectric so that direct electrical contact between the plates could be prevented schematic illustration is shown in Fig 2.1. When the potential difference occurs between the plates of the capacitor, that causes static electric field, which triggers charge accumulation on physically separated electrodes. In these capacitors capacitance is

proportionate to the surface area of the electrodes as well as dielectric constant of dielectric material between the plates. In addition to that lowering the separation within the plates increases the capacitance of conventional capacitors (Halper & Ellenbogen, 2006a).

Figure 2.1 Schematic illustration of Conventional capacitor

2.3.2 Working Principle of electrochemical supercapacitors.

Electrochemical Supercapacitor is the advanced generation of capacitive devices. It delivers higher energy density and power densities compared to their predecessor conventional parallel plate capacitors. Moreover, electrodes used in supercapacitors have higher surface area compared to electrodes being used in conventional capacitors, as well as electrolyte solution with a separator increases the capacitance by many folds (Winter & Brodd, 2004).

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In supercapacitors, a set of two-electrodes is attached to current collectors. Both electrodes are kept apart by a separator and immersed within a closed pack device in an electrolyte. Schematic demonstration of the capacitor is expressed in Fig 2.2. When electrode interacts electrolyte, a layer forms on either side of the electrodes. Which results in the charge separation, making both electrodes behave two supercapacitors connected in series circuit assembly and enhancing gross capacitance of SC device using the formula below 2.1 (Frackowiak et al., 2006; Lota et al., 2008a).

Figure 2.2 Schematic of Supercapacitors

SCs are further classified in three categories EDLCs, Pseudocapacitors and hybrid capacitors. The classification tree is illustrated in Fig 2.3. The classification of SCs rests on their discrete mechanisms, such as electrostatic charge storage, reversible Faradic redox reaction, and a fusion of both (S.-M. Chen et al., 2014).

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Figure 2.3 Classification tree of supercapacitors

Electrical double-layer capacitors (EDLCs)

EDLCs is a type of SC made of two electrodes, electrolyte, and a separator. A schematic display of EDLCs is shown in Fig 2.4. In EDLCs the charge absorption and desorption happen at the interface of electrode and electrolyte making a very thin layer of dielectric. In addition to that high surface area materials such as activated carbon is employed as electrode material in EDLCs (Hall et al., 2010). Since charging and discharging cycles are extremely reversible therefore the cyclic stability of EDLCs is also very high.

Figure 2.4 Schematic illustration of EDLCs

Since the occurrence of double layer is the fundamental of charge storage mechanism in EDLCs. When the voltage is applied, charges start amassing over electrode surface. Electrolyte ions tunnel across the separator and penetrate via pores of the electrodes. Due to applied potential, opposite charges get collected over the junction on the middle of electrode and electrolyte. Henceforth, a double layer of charge is created on either side electrodes. Historically, materials with Carbon constituents have largely been employed in EDLCs.

AC is among the frequently employed electrode material in EDLCs. Their high surface area and low manufacturing cost secure them a suitable candidacy to be used in EDLCs. AC is synthesized from carbon precursors in inert environment by a thorough

process of carbonization and then activation. To enlarge pore volume and surface area oxidation is carried out in CO₂, water vapor or in KOH (Simon & Gogotsi, 2010a; C.-S. Yang et al., 2014). A complex network of interconnected poresize distribution contributes a lot to the enlarge surface area of AC. The greater the surface area is directly proportionate to the specific capacitance, as carbon provides massive interfaces for the formation double layer (Lota et al., 2008b).

However, increased porosity is significant for achieving high values of capacitance. But it also brings some complications to the system. If these poresize is not comparable with the electrolyte ions the charge storage is not likely to happen. For example, it is highly unlikely that charge is stored if poresize is shorter as compared to electrolyte ions (D. Qu & Shi, 1998; H. Shi, 1996). Moreover, high porosity reduces the conductivity, therefore resulting in to limited power density (Vangari et al., 2013). In addition to that, an electrolyte resistance builds up which limits charge discharge rates (Pandolfo & Hollenkamp, 2006).

Another widely used electrode material for EDLCs is Carbon nanotubes (CNTs). Their extraordinary properties including high electric conductivity, poresize, reasonably lofty chemical stability and adequate surface area make them excellent material to be used in EDLCs. Generally, two types of CNTs are used: Single walled carbon nanotubes (SWCNTs) and multiwalled carbon nanotubes (MWCNTs) (Baughman et al., 2002). Mesoporous nature of CNTs in electrodes allows electrolyte to readily diffuse, resulting lower resistance and increased power (An et al., 2001).

Graphene is a 2D carbon allotrope, with hexagonal lattice structure. It is the primary building block of graphitic carbons, fullerenes, CNTs and graphite (Ban et al., 2011). Unique structure of graphene brings excellent properties as it amounts to increased values of surface area, and electrical conductivity, flexibility, and mechanical

properties. Afore mentioned properties make graphene excellent material for SC applications (H.-J. Choi et al., 2012; L. L. Zhang et al., 2010).

Graphene based supercapacitors could offer increased specific capacitance of 117 F/g that is proportionate to AC based electrodes (Stoller et al., 2008). However, graphene and associated materials have been widely investigated for applications in energy storage, but due to limitations and complexity of their synthesis with high purity pose a big hurdle towards their use in in scalable applications (L. L. Zhang et al., 2010).

Graphene oxide reduced from graphite has relatively smooth synthesis method. It has functional group attached to it surface such as Oxygen and these functional groups are instrumental in manifesting supercapacitor applications (Y. Sun et al., 2011). However, surface area of GO is smaller than graphene, but GO manifested high values of capacitance as 189 F/g due to the occupancy of functional groups on the surface. Moreover, graphene oxide showed good cyclic stability. Low manufacturing cost and better performance make graphene oxide a superior electrode material than pristine graphene for SCs (B. Xu et al., 2011).

Pseudocapacitors

Pseudocapacitors is another type of supercapacitors that store energy in reversible redox reactions that occur over electrode surface. In pseudocapacitors for charge storage mechanism usually metal oxides as well as conducting polymers are commissioned as electrode materials (Jayalakshmi & Balasubramanian, 2008; Rudge et al., 1994). Pseudocapacitors exhibit a unique combination of capacitive as well as Faradic charge storage process. Which means in these types of capacitors energy is stored both ways either by undergoing redox reactions and by the charge collection on the surface. Pseudocapacitive materials typically exhibit high surface area and short diffusion pathways that prompt quick charge transfer adequate charge storage. These

nanostructures facilitate high power density as well as outstanding cyclic stability making them a promising material for future work in energy storage. The Redox active materials employed in pseudocapacitors, cause Faradic reactions/processes. These reversible Faradic reactions/processes in pseudocapacitors are attributed to their greater values of specific capacitance as well as higher energy density values than EDLCs. Despite these merits pseudocapacitors suffer from compromised cyclic stability.

Metal oxide-based supercapacitors

Superior electrical conductivity of metal oxides has been pivotal in establishing their role as an electrode material in SCs (Kötz & Carlen, 2000). Such electrodes exhibit high values of specific capacitance and prolonged operational time (Jogade et al., 2011). RuO₂ and MnO₂ have been widely used for pseudocapacitive applications, along with other metal oxides such as TiO₂, CuO (Burke, 2000; I.-H. Kim & Kim, 2001; J. P. Zheng & Jow, 1995). RuO₂ possess excellent pseudocapacitive properties like greater values of specific capacitance, outstanding conductivity as well as thermal stability. During charge discharge cycles series of reversible redox reactions take place and oxidation state changes among Ru⁴⁺, Ru³⁺ and Ru²⁺ (Simon & Gogotsi, 2010b). Hydrated RuO₂ nanostructures when used as electrode material for pseudocapacitive device, showed excellent performance. The obtained value of specific capacitance was as high as 1300F/g, that means this value is higher than conducting polymers and even carbon-based materials. Moreover, ESR values of RuO₂ electrodes were also lower than other contemporary electrodes, proving RuO₂ an excellent material for pseudocapacitors (C.-C. Hu et al., 2006). Generally, Ru based pseudocapacitive electrodes cost high value of production, which limit their use in mass scale.

MnO₂ due to its nontoxic nature, ample presence and cost effectiveness becomes another important metal oxide based electrode material (Davies & Yu, 2011; C. Xu et al., 2010). MnO₂ has been widely studied and its performance evolved and improved with suitable tailoring of the material. Such as, amorphous hydrous MnO₂ electrode material in aqueous electrolyte manifested specific capacitance of 200F/g (H. Y. Lee & Goodenough, 1999). In another study using AC as anode and MnO₂ as cathode a wide operating potential window of 2V was achieved which double of symmetric aqueous supercapacitor (Hong et al., 2002). In another study MnO₂ nanoparticles have been used as active material. Resultantly the achieved specific capacitance value of MnO₂ nanoparticles came out as 297 F/g, that was more than bulk MnO₂ (Devaraj & Munichandraiah, 2006). The properties of MnO₂ nanoparticles related to its structure and morphology where pore and particle size are vital in performance enhancement of SCs (Devaraj et al., 2012).

Conducting polymer-based supercapacitors

Conducting polymer is another popular type of electrode with a wide range of superior electrochemical properties. They offer comparatively high capacitance values, lesser ESR and high conductivity as well as cheap in cost compared to some metal oxides. The conductivity of polymer based SCs comes from a system of conjugated bonds that lies along the polymer (Snook et al., 2011). Charge storage procedure in conducting polymer SCs is relied on redox reactions which means increased energy storage and reduced self-discharge. During oxidation these polymers tend to be *p*-doped with anions and become *n*-doped cations during reduction reactions.

Commonly employed conducting polymers in SCs applications are polyaniline (PANI), polypyrrole (PPy), poly(3,4-ethylenedioxythiophene) (PEDOT), and their derivatives (Sivakkumar & Saraswathi, 2004; K. Wang et al., 2014). For instance,

PANI with careful synthesis parameters can attain towering values of specific capacitance as ~500 F/g in acidic medium (Talbi et al., 2003).

Hybrid supercapacitors

The third and relatively new type of supercapacitor is Hybrid supercapacitor. A hybrid SC is composed of double layer carbon material and a pseudocapacitive material (Y. Zhang et al., 2009). In hybrid supercapacitors the capacitance depends on the capacitance stored by double layer porous carbon materials and pseudocapacitive metal oxides or conducting polymers (Halper & Ellenbogen, 2006b). The idea behind the hybrid supercapacitors is to converge the merits of EDLCs and pseudocapacitors so that a new device is developed with enhanced performance. Hybrid supercapacitors are further categorized in three different types. Asymmetric, battery type hybrids and composite.

Asymmetric hybrid supercapacitors are composed of a combination of EDLC and pseudocapacitive electrodes. The first of its kind hybrid supercapacitor with positive *p*-doped polymer whereas AC be used as negative electrode manifested superior performance with high energy and power densities (Arbizzani et al., 2001; Laforgue et al., 2003; Mastragostino et al., 2002). These supercapacitors can obtain high values of energy density and power density with high values compared to EDLCs as they lack behind. Moreover, the cyclic stability and cyclic performance of asymmetric hybrid SCs is also high making them superior to that of pseudocapacitors.

In composite hybrid supercapacitor, composite materials are used to integrate carbon over pseudocapacitive materials like conducting polymers and metal oxides. Subsequent material is then used as electrode material for SC applications (C. Peng et al., 2008). Porous structure of carbon renders high surface area that flourishes the electrolyte interaction with pseudocapacitive material.

Third category of hybrid SCs is Battery-type SCs, which is also a two-electrode system of different materials: battery electrode and supercapacitor electrode (H. Li et al., 2005; Pell & Conway, 2004; X. Wang & Zheng, 2004). These SCs have a great potential overcome the gap that differentiate batteries from SCs.

2.4 Electrolyte

Electrolyte is another integral part with foremost importance in any energy storage system. Electrolytes used in SCs are further classified in to two categories. Liquid electrolytes and solid-state or quasi-SS electrolytes. A detailed classification chart of electrolytes is shown in Fig. 2.5. There are two more classifications in liquid electrolytes, such as aqueous and non-aqueous electrolytes. Usually aqueous electrolytes are prepared by constituents such as acids (H_2SO_4 , H_3PO_4), salts (KNO_3 , LiCl , Na_2SO_4 , Li_2SO_4) and alkaline materials (LiOH , NaOH) (P.-C. Chen et al., 2010; Horng et al., 2010; McKeown et al., 1999; Meng et al., 2009). Whereas organic electrolytes are prepared by mixing salts and organic solvents (L. Hu et al., 2009; C. Yu et al., 2009). Moreover, organic electrolyte is capable of operating in potential range of 2 to 4 V that is substantially higher than aqueous electrolyte. Supercapacitors have been widely prepared by using liquid electrolytes.

Figure 2.5 Classification of various type of electrolytes (Amaral et al., 2022)

Another very important type of electrolyte is SS electrolyte. The gel electrolytes such as PVA, PVDF and polyvinylidene fluoride-co-hexafluoropropylene (P(VDF-HFP)) (S. Shi, Xu, Yang, Li, et al., 2013). The gel or solid-state electrolytes show great flexibility and displayed excellent performance. The commonly used gel electrolytes are $\text{H}_3\text{PO}_4/\text{PVA}$ (Niu et al., 2013; Z. Yang et al., 2013), KOH/PVA [76], $\text{BMIM}+\text{BF}_4^-$ (1-butyl-3-methylimidazolium tetrafluoroborate) ionic liquid/PVDF (Ho et al., 2008), aqueous $\text{Ca}(\text{NO}_3)_2\text{-SiO}_2$ (S. Shi, Xu, Yang, Chen, et al., 2013) , 1-butyl-3-methylimidazolium chloride ($[\text{BMIM}][\text{Cl}]$) ionic liquid-cellulose (D. Wei et al., 2009). The high conductivity and flexibility of PVA gel electrolyte makes it an excellent candidate for solid-state electrolyte to be used in supercapacitors. This electrolyte is prepared by adding adequate amount of PVA to de-ionized water at 85C while constant stirring. PVA gel performance can be more improved by adding KI as mediator. In a report published by Yu et al. (H. Yu et al., 2011) PVA/KOH-KI gel electrolyte

improved the pseudocapacitance of AC electrode by many folds as compared to simple PVA/KOH electrolyte. Another very important electrolyte material is Nafion used for both electrolyte and separator in SC device assembly. The solid-state supercapacitor device using rGO as electrodes showed doubled performance as compared to solvent Nafion based rGO SC assembly (B. G. Choi et al., 2011).

For any SC electrolyte it is very important to meet some requisites, so that a viable and efficient device could be developed. High ionic conductivity, mechanical strength, EC stability and wide operating potential window are fundamentals for any efficient electrolyte. Charged polymer chains are responsible for ionic conductivity in polymer based electrolytes (Łatoszyńska et al., 2015). They are made of repeated monomer chained together through covalent bonds; these monomers can also be called as structural units of the polymer which means they possess plenty of elemental units (Amaral et al., 2022).

Gel polymer electrolytes (GPE)

In gel polymer electrolyte polymer and solvent are connected in a polymer matrix. Gel electrolytes endure properties both from liquid and solid electrolytes and at times do not require a separator (Osada et al., 2016). One of the key aspects of gel electrolytes is their flexibility; and this flexibility makes them constitute SCs with great flexibility, safety, and lesser weight. The properties of these GPEs greatly depend on the polymer structure to be used in gel making, moreover their interaction with the solvents is also important. The presence of solvents in the gel, enhances their mobility (Choudhury et al., 2009; Sekhon, 2003).

Generally, GPEs have salts which provide them with free ions and thus contribute to conductivity, whereas solvents help in providing a conducting medium and contribute to solvating the salts. Polymers used in GPEs due to their viscosity give mechanical

stability to the SCs. It is also important that potential salts be used must possess large anions and low dissociation energy, meanwhile solvents should endure high values of dielectric constant, along with less viscosity, high boiling, and low melting points (Choudhury et al., 2009; Sekhon, 2003). GPEs are classified in to three major types such as hydrogels, organogels and iongels.

2.5 MXene

MXene is a relatively new inclusion in 2D materials family, made of metal carbides, metal nitrides and carbon nitrides. They possess high electrical conductivity with greater redox active sites, thickness controllability and excellent surface chemistry (J. Luo et al., 2020). These remarkable physical as well as chemical properties associated with MXene make it an exceptional material to be used in energy storage and harvesting devices. MXene is prepared when A material is etched out from original MAX phase, here M shows transition metals, whereas A is for group III, or IV elements and X shows carbides or nitrides. Generally, MXene is exfoliated from bulk precursors with layered structures bonded together with weak van der Waal forces (Naguib et al., 2012a). The MAX phases exhibit a unique combination of properties, that involves ceramic as well as metallic nature. Their brittleness, thermal stability, mechanical stiffness amounts to ceramic nature, whereas good heat and electrical conductivity is due to metallic nature (Barsoum, 2013; Ouisse & Barsoum, 2017). The parent MAX phases hail from group $D_{6h}-P6_3/mmc$ with layered hexagonal structure where M layers are interspersed with A layers and octahedral sites are inhabited with X atoms (Barsoum, 2000). The M-A bond is metallic in nature which is so strong in contrast with graphene and TMDs that endure Vander-walls bonding, whereas bond M-X has a bond nature either of these metallic, covalent, or ionic. M-X bond is slightly

stronger than metallic bond of M-A that contributes to etch out A layers to achieve MXene (Naguib, Mochalin, et al., 2014).

Targeted A layer etching from its parent MAX phase concludes in emergence of MXene. These new layered materials possess different properties from their layered three-dimensional (3D) precursors. Generally, MXene is expressed as $M_{n+1}X_nT_x$, “n” is a range that spans over 1 to 3, T depicts functional groups like (-O, -F and -OH) (Cui et al., 2017; Wesolowski et al., 2015). Normally, “n” values are proportionate to stability, the higher the “n” value higher will be the stability of MXene. These functional groups get created while etching procedure in the presence of acid. This etching also contributes to the hydrophilicity of MXene. Presence of ternary groups over its surface impact the electronic and ionic transportation of the MXene which effect its conductivity (Sinha et al., 2018). Possible MXene lattice structures can exist in three different formations such as M_2X , M_3X_2 and M_4X_3 as shown in Fig 2.5 (Naguib, Mochalin, et al., 2014).

A range of MXene have been identified to date which include $V_2C_2T_x$, $Ti_3C_2T_x$, and Ti_2CT_x (Naguib et al., 2012b, 2013). Presently a hundred or even more MAX phases are introduced from various combinations of three elements of MAX phases (Z. Liu et al., 2014). So far three different lattice structures of MXene have been reported such as M_2X , M_3X_2 , M_4X_3 (Naguib, Mochalin, et al., 2014). $Ti_3C_2T_x$ is among the earliest and vastly studied MXene, redox active chemistry, metallic conductivity and hydrophilicity are the glaring aspects of $Ti_3C_2T_x$ MXene. Unique metallic and ceramic combination of MXene have been vastly used in a variety of fields. Surface chemistry

of MXene give rise to a wide spectrum of properties like high thermal and metallic conductivity, electric and magnetic properties, increased hydrophilicity as well as optical properties (Panda et al., 2022).

Due to high conductivity, hydrophilicity, ion intercalation, as well as high mechanical strength and volumetric specific capacity, MXene offer high power density than various semiconductor metal oxides that is helpful in quick charging of storage devices. Plentiful presence of functional groups over ($\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{T}_x$) MXene surface make it a suitable candidate over other contemporary 2D materials including layer chalcogenides and graphene (Augustyn et al., 2013; Naguib et al., 2012b). A variety of factors determine the properties and establish potential applications of MXene, such as elemental composition, stoichiometry, synthesis routes, gaps between the layers and their thickness (Y. Wei et al., 2021). Nitride based MXene hold better electrical conductivity but lesser structural stability than Carbide based MXene (N. Zhang et al., 2018). Due to supercapacitive properties of MXene, its composites have been widely used as pseudocapacitive material (Q. Jiang et al., 2018). $\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{T}_x$ MXene rendered excellent electrochemical properties when employed as SC electrode material due to their lower molecular weight (Fang et al., 2020). MXene has been used both as composite with different materials as well as stand alone.

The charge storing mechanism in MXene sheets is quite distinguishable for EDLCs and pseudocapacitors. In EDLC based MXene SCs, improved charge storing process is associated with enlarged electrode surface area. Meanwhile, MXene based pseudocapacitors store charges via reversible ion intercalation at reactive sites on the MXene sheets in an aqueous media. The advanced characterization techniques including electronic conductance measurements, in situ electrochemical impedance,

and Electrochemical quartz crystal admittance (EQCA) greatly favors the facile and profound cation adsorption sites within $\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{T}_x$ MXene layers (Shao et al., 2019). The preliminary adsorption of ions occurs at the facile adsorption sites near at the periphery of the layers, followed by further ions adsorption at inner adsorption sites with increased activation energy. Such step-wise adsorption of ions at MXene sheets are of great importance such as under increased scan rate ions readily get adsorbed at shallow adsorption sites, causing an eximious rate performance of MXene. On the other hand, the ions get desorbed from in-depth adsorption areas at a higher potential inducing the high faradic efficiency and retained the good stability of MXene electrodes (Levi et al., 2015).

The confined water molecules within the layers greatly improve the gravimetric capacitance. Besides, it is suggested that small sized cations with higher charges, lessen the interlayer spacing, whereas large sized cations with smaller oxidation state increase the interlayer spacing. A single intercalated Li^+ ions resemble to the insertion of one H_2O molecule within the interlayers. Moreover, the Mxene electrodes repeatedly get stiffened and softened due to reversible intercalation of Li^+ ions and their deintercalation (J. Luo et al., 2017). The morphological analysis reveals the decreased interlayer spacing within the $\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{T}_x$ sheets due to intercalated Li^+ , Mg^{2+} , or Na^+ cations. Such decreased interlayer spacing of MXene sheets due to cations insertion is opposite to the volumetric expansion behavior of other bulk phase 2D sheets such as Graphite, and Silicon upon redox active ions intercalation (J. Tang et al., 2021). Therefore, the ionic radius and oxidation state of intercalated cations greatly affect layer spacing of MXene sheets, therefore the reduced interlayer separation of MXene sheets due to Li^+ and Mg^{2+} ions provide favorable features for increased volumetric capacitance with good stability (Forouzandeh & Pillai, 2021a).

Structure of MXene

MXenes like their parent MAX phases have closed packed layered hexagonal structures (Naguib, Mochalin, et al., 2014). In layered MXene structures usually an X layer is stacked between the M layers in an arrangement as $[MX]_nM$. Apart from usual MXene structures, double MXenes contain two M elements that remain in two distinct shapes, solid solutions and arranged phases. Density functional theory (DFT) studies have revealed that ordered phases have higher stability as compared to solid solution phases (Anasori et al., 2015). Since MXenes have hexagonal structures, therefore their lattice parameters differ subject to opted synthesis routes. The transformation of MAX phases in MXene have increased their lattice parameters (Naguib et al., 2015). Careful modeling and calculations of MXenes have revealed that M atoms lie at lattice points of hcp whilst X atoms sit at octahedral gaps (C. Shi et al., 2014).

So far three different types of MAX phases have been introduced subject to the values of n ($n=1,2,3$) such as M_2AX , M_3AX_2 , and M_4AX_3 . The Fig. 2.5 shows MAX phases and derived MXene structures (Naguib, Mochalin, et al., 2014). Amid these phases, 211 phase has been widely studied and thoroughly investigated for various application. The layer order in M_2X phases of MXene, possess layer pattern as XYXYXY, while in M_3X_2 and M_4X_3 MXenes atoms are ordered in XYZXYZ pattern (Nan et al., 2021a). A variety of MXenes have been prepared, with huge structural similarities with graphene. Layered 2D materials be it MXene or graphene have capability to harbor cations with discrete dimensions. The capacity to harbor cations is known as intercalation (Garg et al., 2020a).

MXene synthesis routes

MXene synthesis have been classified in to two types. Top-down approach and bottom-up approach. In top-down synthesis route, MXene sheets get extracted from

parent MAX or non-MAX phases precursors. Whereas, in bottom-up approach different elements get blended to shape in to thin MXene sheets. A variety of aspects that define structure, characteristics, and properties of MXene are based on the methods used for their fabrication. Therefore, synthesis routes are vital in establishing the nature of MXene. A complete flow chart for the preparation of MXene using different approaches is shown below in Fig. 2.6. Top-down synthesis methods have been further discussed in detail below.

Figure 2.7 Flowchart for MXene preparation using different approaches

Top-down synthesis approach

The standard procedure to extract a 2D structure from parent 3D structure is to extract a layered structure by weakening the bonds between the layers of 3D materials. Etching procedures used for the extraction of 2D structures could either be mechanical or chemical. Since strong bonding exists between the layers of MAX phases particularly M and A layers usually covalent, or metallic bonds are found. These bonds thus avert mechanical shearing, which prevents actualization of layered MXene structure. Therefore, MXenes are prepared by selective chemical etching or temperature treatment (Verger et al., 2019). As A must be exfoliated out of the MAX precursor to materialize MXene structures, therefore it is witnessed that electron insertion in the MAX contribute to the expansion of M-A bond. These expanded bonds thus ease the process of etching out the A layers. Contrary to that induction of positive charges contracts the bond between M-A, this bond shrinking makes it difficult to exfoliate A layers of the MAX phases (Khazaei et al., 2018). Henceforth, it is also established that using electron induction while etching process makes exfoliation easier.

A variety of chemical etchants have been used to exfoliate MAX phases such as hydrofluoric acid(HF), acid/fluoride salt, alkalis, electrochemical, molten salt and many more. Since this etching procedure not only sums in the exfoliation of A from the MAX phase but also contribute in establishing surface ternary groups like -O,-OH and -F. These ternary groups not just help in stabilizing the MXene structures, but they are vital in determining the MXene properties (Wesolowski et al., 2015). Many parameters impact the overall etching procedure to establish the standard of MXene, such as time, temperature, material concentration, etchant etc. These parameters are needed to be carefully monitored, like higher atomic number of M as well as higher

acidic concentration need prolonged etching spans, but it concludes in structural disorientation with defects (Naguib et al., 2012c). Some etching processes are discussed below.

The temperature treatment etching is an important etching procedure. Since M-A bond is metallic, therefore high temperature treatment is helpful in breaking this bond. Despite of that, the high-temperature involvement can damage the layered structures of MAX phases thus turning them in to bulk solid structures leaving vacancies in X. The possible equation could be written as under (Naguib, Presser, et al., 2011).

HF treatment is another and commonly used etching procedure, to synthesize MXene. In this procedure, A layer is etched out of the precursor phase MAX by immersing powder MAX powder in HF. Hence selective etching is achieved, along with the formation of surface ternary groups. After the etching procedure, vigorous sonication is carried out which helps in actualization of distinct MXene sheets. The obtained product is then washed out to remove acid residual and normalize the pH value (Naguib et al., 2012c). The possible reactions are predicted as under.

Another method of synthesizing MXene from the MAX phases is Electrochemical etching. In this method A layer is etched from MAX phase by applying certain

potential. Here, MAX phases are used as electrode material, dipped in electrolytes like HCl, NaCl, NH₄Cl (W. Sun et al., 2017). This way a fluoride free MXene can be achieved, which has better electrochemical performance than MXene obtained from HF etching (Alhabeab et al., 2018). The etching for longer time is helpful in removing A layer but due to longer period of etching carbide-driven carbon (CDC) results as the final product (S. Yang et al., 2018). Electrochemical etching is an efficient method to prepare hydrophilic MXene with discrete sheet structure, but it gives lesser yield which is a drawback along with CDC. It is of great importance to devise new methods to synthesize CDC free MXene with high yield.

Alkali etching is method is also very instrumental if -F based surface functional groups are aimed to avoided. Moreover, since HF etching involves high risk, due to its hazardous and dangerous nature, therefore alkali etching offers an alternate to that type of etching. Tetramethylammonium hydroxide (TMAOH) is an organic base which is reported to synthesize discrete Ti₃C₂T_x MXene flakes (Xuan et al., 2016). Whereas, on another occasion, Ti₃C₂(OH)₂ is synthesized by using KOH at 180⁰C for 24 hours (G. Li et al., 2017). NaOH has also been reported for the MXene synthesis in Ar presence (T. Li et al., 2018). In alkali etching, the obtained MXene shows larger gaps with negligible presence of -F content, but it is difficult to achieve scalable yield as higher concentration of etchants gives lesser MXene flakes.

Electronic properties of MXene

The chemically diverse surface terminal groups largely affect the electronic features of MXene by modulating the energy bandgap of MXene sheets. For instance, the pure MXene Ti₃C₂ sheets exhibit metallic conductivity, but the introduced terminal functionalities like F or OH imparts semi-conductivity with a bandgap of 0.05 eV and 0.1 eV respectively. Therefore, the tunable energy band gaps of surface terminated

MXene sheets have huge importance in applications related to electronic devices (Bandyopadhyay et al., 2018). The single electron withdrawing nature of fluorine and hydroxide terminated functional groups modulate the electronic features of MXene in a similar fashion but different from highly electronegative oxygenated functional groups. In pure MXene sheets, the conductivity is governed by the d-bands of the transition metal “M”. lying near to their Fermi energies level (Y. Lee, Cho, et al., 2014). In chemically diverse MXene, the p-orbitals of nitrides or carbides exist under the d bands of transition metal atoms with a short bandgap. Furthermore, the further hybridization of p-orbitals of surface terminals F, OH, or O with d-bands of transition metal atoms favorably generated new energy levels below the Fermi energy. This stimulates the further restructuring of energy band scaffold by shifting the Fermi energy level in between d-bands of M transition metal atoms and p-bands of X atoms (J. Yang et al., 2016). The first principal postulates support the existence of Nearly Free Electron states (NFE) near to the Fermi level in MXene sheets terminated with OH functionalities due to positively charged H_2 species at the surface. The electronegativity difference induces a dipole moment and encourages the swift flow of electrons thus exhibiting the semi-conductance behavior of functionalized MXenes. Depending upon the chemical nature of functional groups, the F and O terminated MXene hold NFE states at comparatively increased energy level whereas the NFE states in OH terminated MXenes are nearer to the Fermi level, thus partly occupied as compared to other 2D materials including graphene, graphene, h-BN, and MoS_2 where unoccupied NFE states are situated far away from the Fermi level. Such existence of NFE states is of great importance for nano-electronic device applications due to effective electron conduction through favorable transmission channels unaffected by nuclear scattering (Khazaei et al., 2017). Besides, the energy scaffold and conduction

properties of MXene sheets can also be perturbed through number of layers and their thickness. It has been proven experimentally that weakly coupled MXene sheets lowers the energy bandgap values due to increased number of layers. The atoms of transition metals in the exterior layer impart a dominant role in modulating the electronic features of MXene sheets in comparison of inner layer atoms. The overlapping of Ti atoms with C or N atom greatly decreases the contribution of Ti d-orbitals in the Fermi level (Khazaei et al., 2013). Moreover, titanium nitrides display metallic conductivity than titanium carbide because of the additional electron in nitrogen atom in comparison with carbon atom. Along with terminal functional groups, the chemical nature of transition metal atoms greatly alters the electronic scaffold of MXene sheets. For instance, the addition of molybdenum Mo atoms at the two substituted Ti atoms sites in the MXene $\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2(\text{OH})_2$ modifies its conductance nature from metallic to semiconducting with a low width energy bandgap of 0.05 eV. Such transition of conductance behavior in doped MXene sheets can be referred to low unfilled p orbitals of OH than O (Forouzandeh & Pillai, 2021b). Besides, the substituted N, F, and S atoms at the location of C atoms in MXene scaffold concluded in the transformation of semiconductor to metallic nature of MXene. Likewise, the defects in MXene framework also transforms the metal conductance of MXene into semi conductance or vice versa. One of its experimental pieces of evidence is the band modulating through applied strain such as the band gap became narrower upon increasing the tensile strain. Upon reaching a certain critical value of applied strain, the indirect bandgap transforms into a direct bandgap. Additionally, the externally applied electric field also modulates the bandgap of Sc_2CO_2 MXene from indirect to direct since the electrons of lowest conduction band greatly responds to the electric field (Y. Lee, Hwang, et al., 2014). Likewise, the work function of MXene sheets can

also be tuned by varying the energy band scaffold. The in-situ functionalization of MXene sheets during its synthesis alters the electrostatic potential near the surface resulted into the shift of Fermi level. The electrostatic potential and surface dipole moment are deeply associated with the work function. The surface functionalization alters the surface dipole moment, showing the redistributed surface charge density, and surface atomic relaxation, thus changing the polarity of groups and ultimately alters the work function.

MXene for supercapacitors

Due to supercapacitive properties of MXene, its composites have been widely used as pseudocapacitive material (Q. Jiang et al., 2018). $Ti_3C_2T_x$ MXene holds eximious electrochemical features shown in fig as super capacitive electrode material (Fang et al., 2020). Nevertheless, MXenes still have some issues that are required to be resolved, such as their quick tendency towards restacking that reduces the interlayer gaps hence lessen the transport and diffusion channels for electrolyte ions, particularly the organic electrolyte ions. Thus, greatly affecting the energy storing features of MXenes as super capacitive electrode material. Besides, MXenes are also readily prone to oxidation at higher anodic potentials, lowering the cyclic efficiency and lifespan.

The supercapacitance efficiency of MXene based devices is largely affected by the several factors including synthesis techniques, morphological feature, electrolyte, and interplanar spacings. In MXene sheets, the real cause of pseudocapacitance is incepted from the redox active sites with quick intercalation of ions. Therefore, greater interlayer spacings encourage dense coverage of intercalated electrolyte ions facilitating the improved energy density. For this purpose, sonication or intercalation assisted delamination of MXene sheets are widely suggested techniques to intensify

the specific capacitance for effective accommodation of cations/large active molecules (Maleski et al., 2018). Likewise, the electrochemical features of MXenes are greatly influenced by the selection of starting materials the synthesis of MXene phase (Forouzandeh & Pillai, 2021c). Supercapacitance efficiency of MXene sheets is greatly influenced by the lateral dimensions of synthesized sheets during etching process. The MXene sheets of large sized requires longer etching time which is found not to be very suitable due to low capacitance values within the range of 10–20 F/g. On the other hand, MXene sheets of low dimensions are greatly desired for improved supercapacitor performance due to dense electrochemically active sites over the surface during charging-discharging process. However, MXene sheets with small size are more prone towards speedy oxidation reactions at their terminals. Furthermore, the inherent morphological features of MXene also greatly alter the supercapacitor mechanism of MXene such as thickness of multilayer MXene sheets (Garg et al., 2020b). MXene sheets small lateral dimensions are effective for ion conduction and boost up the supercapacitive performance. Highly delaminated MXenes are the most promising candidates for energy storing devices since single layered structure provides significant adsorption/desorption of ions and an effective surface area for the adsorption and mobility of charges (Nan et al., 2021b). Apart from single layered and multilayered scaffold, a porous framework is also beneficial for increased electrochemical activity due to greater accessibility of electrolyte ions at electrochemically active pore sites. The coating thickness is a significant factor in evaluating the supercapacitor performance. MXene based composite electrodes are usually fabricated through coating procedures including drop casting or slurry coating over porous electrically conductive substrates. Electrodes thickness within the range of 0.4 mm are preferred for a better performance of electrode material. The chemical

nature of terminal functional groups in MXene sheets greatly alter their capacitive performance such as oxygenated functional groups are more effective in enhancing the supercapacitance performance than fluorine terminated functional groups. Since oxygen functional groups form hydroxyl bonds particularly in acidic electrolytes through proton exchange. Likewise, Cl functionalized MXene sheets have considerably high interlayer spacing due to increased ionic radius of chlorine thus providing higher ion diffusion for supercapacitors (Baig et al., 2022).

The supercapacitance performance is also greatly dependent upon electrolyte medium. Generally, the electrolytes are categorized into four classes: aqueous, organic, ionic and solid. The chemical nature of electrolyte mainly determines the working potential window of supercapacitor. MXene sheets exhibit appreciable features of pseudo capacitance for improved volumetric capacitance. Besides, the good mechanical strength and self-assembling features of MXene sheets are highly advantageous for the fabrication of flexible electrode material (F. Li et al., 2022). The advanced flexible features of MXene based electrodes can be achieved by adding organic reinforcements in addition of interlayer spacers. In a nutshell, the energy storing features of MXene based electrodes can be improved through an optimized synthesis scheme of multilayer MXene sheets with enlarged interlayer spacing and well-regulated surface terminal functional groups (Thomas et al., 2022a). MXene properties in SCs are shown in Fig. 2.8.

Figure 2.8 Properties of MXenes for supercapacitor applications (Thomas et al., 2022b)

2.5 Metal Organic Frameworks (MOF)

Metal organic frameworks have gained huge recognition in recent past since their discovery in 1995. MOFs a type of material with porous structure first introduced by Yaghi and team (Yaghi & Li, 1995). This unique material is composed of metal units caged with organic linkers with high crystallinity (L. Wang et al., 2016). By introducing different alterations and structural variations a huge range of MOFs have been developed and the number is still counting (Férey, 2008; Furukawa et al., 2013a; Yot et al., 2014). Due to their unique structure MOFs have versatile properties ranging from gas storage and separation (J.-R. Li et al., 2009; Murray et al., 2009), sensing devices (Guo et al., 2014; Meilikhov et al., 2013; Takashima et al., 2011) , as well as drug delivery (Horcajada et al., 2006, 2010; Kundu et al., 2014).

MOFs are classified as materials possessing towering crystallinity and porous structures where organic linkers are used to create bonds between metal units called SBUs (secondary building units). The high crystallinity, high porosity, and size

alterations in MOFs bring redox active sites which make them suitable candidate for electrochemical applications (J. Kim et al., 2017; Ramachandran, Zhao, et al., 2018). When metallic units are combined with negatively charged units which are usually ditopic or polytopic organic carboxylates some sturdy material architectures are formed. These strong architectures are highly porous and crystalline their porosity is much higher than its overall crystal volume (Zhou et al., 2012). MOFs offer a high surface area as compared to other contemporary porous structures such as zeolites or carbon structures, typically MOFs possess surface area with wide range of 1000 to 10,000 m²/g. Due to flexibility of various factors such as size, constituents and geometry thousands of MOFs structures have been reported (Furukawa et al., 2013b).

Structure of MOF

MOFs are classified in to two types based on SBU, finite and infinite metal-containing SBUs. Finite metal-containing SBUs have metal-oxygen polyhedral are linked in rings. Whereas infinite metal containing SBUs also known as rods, are infinitely linked in one dimension (Rosi et al., 2005). These rod MOFs due to their quality properties have attracted huge applications in various fields. The stability of MOFs has been a cause of concern for the researchers for a long time. Although initially reported from divalent metals MOFs such as Cu²⁺ or Zn²⁺ attained high porosity and surface area but could not prove stability when challenged for stability test in rigorous conditions. So much so MOF-5 another very important class of MOFs structure slowly started decomposing when exposed to ambient atmosphere (Yuan et al., 2018). Therefore, it is desirable to design such MOFs structures that have frameworks integrity that could sustain stability in harsh conditions.

Synthesis of MOF

Numerous synthesis methods are reported to synthesize MOFs structures up till now. One of the initial and commonly used method to synthesize MOFs is Solvothermal method. There are some other routes that have been opted to prepare MOFs like, solvothermal, electrochemistry, hydrothermal, template, microwave, sol-gel, mechanochemical, sonochemical, atomic layer deposition (ALD), supercritical and flow chemistry (Rubio-Martinez et al., 2017). Few of these techniques are briefly discussed below.

Solvothermal method usually used in lab scale production that yields MOFs in grams. In solvothermal method, inorganic salts and organic linkers get mixed in selective solvents. The mixture is secured in vessels and heated at certain temperatures to grow frameworks that precipitate in the form of fine crystals (Çolak et al., 2011). These sealed vessels heat the solvents beyond their boiling points hence pressure increases and make the constituents soluble. This benchmark method has been vital in synthesizing thousands for MOFs structures. However, this method is excellent for the lab scale production but it's not suitable for mass production of MOFs (Rubio-Martinez et al., 2017).

Electrochemical synthesis is relatively new route to prepare MOFs. Here electrical energy is used to induce such chemical reactions that subsequently produce MOFs structures. First time electrochemistry was used in 2005 for the synthesis of MOF (Mueller et al., 2006). This synthesis involves a metal plate electrode that acts as ion source, dipped in solution. The solution contains organic linkers such as benzenetricarboxylic (BTC) or BDC and electrolyte. When a certain potential or current is passed through solution, ion release takes place from metal plate in solution

and thus reacts with the linker. The obtained surface area using this method is higher than the MOFs produced by solvothermal method. Fig. 2.9 shows assembly of electrochemical route for MOF synthesis.

Figure 2.9 Electrochemical assembly for MOF synthesis

Microwave (MW) synthesis has a rich history of synthesizing various materials in organic chemistry. Therefore, it has also been used to synthesize MOFs along with other nanomaterials such as zeolites and inorganic materials (Bilecka & Niederberger, 2010; Gharibeh et al., 2009; Khan & Jung, 2015). In this method electromagnetic waves are made to interact with materials like solvents containing polar molecules or conducting ions in solids. In MW synthesis electromagnetic waves irradiate the solvent thus resulting in heating up the reactants. The crystallization process occurs on the hotspots where direct contact of solvent and MW occurs, which gives a faster reaction and yields fine crystals with small particle size.

Mechanochemical synthesis is believed to be the simplest, cost effective and environmentally clean synthesis method of all to be employed for MOFs synthesis. Mechanochemical synthesis has been quite common over the past in the field of metallurgy and mineral processing, whereas lately this method has also been used in numerous experiments of chemistry like catalysis, inorganic chemistry, and pharmaceutical synthesis (Rubio-Martinez et al., 2017). Rationale is to carry out chemical reaction either by milling or grinding the solid with little or no use of any solvent (Stolle et al., 2011). Tools like mortar and pestle or ball milling are used to carry out this method. The method is further classified in to three different classes, such as solvent free grinding where any kind of solvents are avoided; liquid assisted grinding which is fast because it utilizes catalytic amounts of liquid phases; ion and liquid assisted grinding where catalytic liquids are used with little presence of salts to speed up MOF production.

MOFs for Supercapacitors

In recent years, a wide variety of literature has been devoted on exploring the features of MOFs as supercapacitance electrode material due to enlarged surface area and redox-reactive metal centers for effective ion intercalation/de-intercalation in the course of charge-discharge events. Moreover, MOFs can also be used as sacrificial templates/starting materials for the fabrication of well-regulated porous carbon morphology, metallic hydroxides, metal sulfides / phosphides with micro/nano-structuring in terms of well-organized metal nodes and organic ligands within the crystalline scaffold of MOFs. Nevertheless, the supercapacitance performance of MOFs in its pristine form is limited due to some intrinsic limiting factors such as poor electrical conductance as well as degradation in the electrolyte. Considerable attempts have been made to overcome these challenges, including combining the MOFs

scaffold with conductive substances such as carbonaceous materials and conductive macromolecules. These composites showed improved electrochemical activity due to synergistic effects, for instances, the vertically oriented nickel based 2D MOF@carbon nano-walls exhibited increased specific capacitance 1962 F/g at a current density of 1A/g with working potential window of 0.45 V. In another literature, Ni and Co functionalized 2D MOF@reduced graphene oxide through co-precipitation at room temperature was marked with a high specific capacitance (Souri et al., 2022).

2.6 Stand-alone MXene and MOF electrode limitations

To overcome the above stated limitations of MXene sheets (stacked layers, rapid oxidation, and sluggish charge storage kinetics), the synthesis of hybrid structures, surface functionalization and heteroatom doping are greatly suggested for effective supercapacitor electrode material. The combination of different materials induces significant functional properties, entirely different from the parent components. For this purpose, MXene sheets have been coupled with electro active materials, including metallic ions, carbon materials, and conducting organic molecules. This approach provides the concept of super catalyst with outstanding electronic conductance due to quick electron conduction, increased reactive sites, and stabilized materials' scaffold. Consequently, MXene-based nanostructures exhibit eximious electrochemical activity in comparison of MXene alone as well as other components of composites (M. Hu et al., 2020). The in-situ growth of various active materials at MXene sheets effectively inhibit the restacking issues of MXene sheets thus enhancing the ion conduction and accessibility. Besides, the working potential window of MXenes in aqueous electrolytes is not practically wide that impedes high energy capacity of the fabricated symmetric supercapacitors (Murugesan & Raja, 2023). On the other hand, fabricating asymmetric supercapacitors for high energy application is a viable approach. However,

the restricted capacitance of double layer capacitive electrode materials also restricts the supercapacitors in terms of high energy density. Therefore, pseudocapacitive and battery type electrode materials are highly recommended (Gogotsi & Penner, 2018). In a similar manner, the bare 2D-MOF is not ideal due to inherent agglomeration or stacked layers causing insignificant electrochemical activity and lower accessibility of electrolyte ions with the electrode surface area. Moreover, the poor conductance of this 2D-MOF electrode material causes huge potential drop and narrower domain of working potential. Fortunately, all these issues of MOF could be overcome through nano-structuring, regulating the crystallinity and chemical functionalization (H. Gao et al., 2021). Porous nano-structuring in 2D materials provide enlarged surface area in comparison of layered hydroxides thus enhancing the electrode–electrolyte interaction for greater electrolyte ion accessibility and limits the electrode polarization while charging and discharging events. Besides, amorphous phase greatly contributes towards the increased electrochemical performance due to structural disordering. Such structural disordering constitutes lots of unsatisfying bonds that lead to synergistic interaction of ions with the electrode material, and improved structural stability towards regular charge-discharge events. The conductance property of pristine MOF can also be improved through three-dimensional 3D networking of conjugate systems thus enhancing the performance of MOF based electrode materials for energy storage and conversion applications (Mohanty et al., 2021). Consequently, the pore tuning, structural engineering, and tuned crystallographic features of MOFs can greatly alter their electrochemical activity.

2.7 Rational behind MXene-MOF composite electrode

The two chemically different layered materials can be coupled together to form a superlattice 2D/2D architectures with improved charge storing ability and electrochemical firmness. Such two-dimensional heterostructures are highly efficient in overcoming the stacking issues of layered material as well as shorten the diffusion path for ions/electrons. Due to effective 2D morphology engineering, the enhanced pseudocapacitance and/or EDLC, improved rate capability and longevity of charge storing devices can be achieved (Nasrin et al., 2022). For this purpose, MXene sheets are incorporated within the MOFs framework to synthesize high-performance supercapacitor materials in terms of high specific capacity and cycling stability (D. Xu et al., 2023). Pang and co-workers fabricated 3D porous $\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{T}_x/\text{ZIF-67}/\text{CoV}_2\text{O}_6$ through “ion conversion and exchange” for high-efficiency supercapacitors. The synthesized 2D composite favors the quick ion/electron migration at MXene interface with MOF.

Moreover, the 1D morphology of porous Co-Fe oxide nanorods derived from MOF was independently grown on MXene films. The Co-Fe oxide/ $\text{Ti}_3\text{C}_2\text{T}_x$ hetero junction exhibited 2467.6F cm^{-3} volume capacity in 1 M LiCl solution. However, the same heterojunction exhibited 356.4 mF c^{-2} capacitance as an a-symmetric device with excellent cycling performance (88.2% capacitance retention after 10,000 cycles) (X. Liu et al., 2022). Likewise, the other 1D MOF derived MXene based combination prepared through thermal treatment of Ni- MOFs/MXene/Ni foam at 300°C marked the high performance as hybrid supercapacitor in terms of increased specific capacity. Besides, 1D nanostructure, the unique hexagons of Ni-Co@NiCo-MOFs were synthesized on foam nickel in a well-regulated arrangement for enhanced longevity of

the charge storing device due to greater number of effective channels for speedy ion/electron conduction (S. Zheng et al., 2022).

Due to increased metallic conductivity and super hydrophilic nature, MXene sheets preferable accommodate a wide range of cations either with or without polarizing the MXene-electrolyte interface. Particularly, in acidic electrolytes, MXenes exhibit intense pseudocapacitive nature because of the protonation tendency of oxy functional moieties followed by the change in valence state of transition metal atoms. The efficient capacitance of multi-layered MXene electrodes at hundreds of microns were achieved by Vertical alignment of MXene sheets via liquid crystalline approach. Mxene based flexible electrodes for high performance supercapacitors were fabricated by utilizing a MOF-derived 1D porous CoFe oxide (W. Xie et al., 2020). In the prepared composite MXene not only acted as a conductive agent but also as a binder to coat Co/Fe oxide thus facilitated enhanced charge-transfer kinetics with eximious mechanical strength. Since the well grown CoFe oxide porous structure acted as a spacer for enhanced interlayer distance, thus facilitating the effective ion conducting channels. Since MXenes possess higher capacitance in acidic electrolytes whereas MOF and MOF-derived electrodes hold good charge storing features in neutral and basic electrolytes. Therefore, 2D heterojunctions of MXene with MOF enable the nanocomposite to withstand in acidic/basic electrolyte (Zhuang et al., 2023). The coupling of MXene sheets with nitrogen-doped porous carbonaceous framework is a viable approach to inhibit the agglomeration factors of MXene sheets, thus improving the electrochemical activity. In such combinations the organic linkers in the framework impart an important role for π -conjugated structure, for quick charge conduction with improved capacitance and cycling repeatability (Saini et al., 2021). Thus, it is believed

that MXene based nanostructures and modified architectures will introduce a wide variety of opportunities for the exploration of upcoming energy storage devices.

Discussion

Since batteries suffer from low power density, whereas SCs predominantly EDLCs have low values of energy density. Therefore, it is important to fabricate materials and devices that could generate optimum values of energy and power density while having typical SC cyclic life. Pseudocapacitors especially battery-type SCs can be an excellent alternate to this issue. In conclusion, battery-type SC are supposed to have the potential to bridge the gap between batteries and SCs. If some structural defects, and stability issues associated with these electrodes are addressed, these electrodes can be an alternate energy storage in the future. This work will be based on the these gaps, a new material design is to be proposed between MOFs and MXene, that should be able enough to provide ground for efficient devices and pave a way for future work.

Chapter 3. Materials and methodology

In this chapter, chemicals, experimental techniques, characterization equipment have been discussed in detail. Since three different active electrodes and an AC based negative electrode was prepared to assemble the ASC. Therefore, their synthesis procedures are discussed separately in different sections of this chapter.

3.1 Chemicals, reagents, and apparatuses

High graded analytical chemicals were utilized during the course of experiments, and no extra purification was carried out. Titanium aluminum carbide Ti_3AlC_2 powder, 48% Hydrofluoric acid (HF), cobalt nitrate hexahydrate $(Co(NO_3)_2 \cdot 6H_2O)$, copper nitrate trihydrate $Cu(NO_3)_2 \cdot 3H_2O$, terephthalic acid H_2BDC , iron chloride hexahydrate $FeCl_3 \cdot 6H_2O$, Dimethylformamide (DMF), 2-methylimidazol $C_4H_6N_2$, sodium sulfide nonahydrate $(Na_2S \cdot 9H_2O)$, activated carbon (AC), potassium hydroxide (KOH), polyvinyl alcohol (PVA), deionized water (DI) was employed at various steps of experiments. Most of the chemicals were procured from Sigma-Aldrich.

Semi micro balance was used to precisely scale the materials with accurate concentrations. Hot plates and magnetic stirrers were used to mix the desired materials in the solvents. Teflon lined autoclaves, vacuum oven, and high RMP centrifuge were used to carryout crucial steps of the experiments.

3.2 Synthesis and development of electrode materials

Here material synthesis, and their subsequent growth on substrate is thoroughly discussed. The preparation started from the synthesis of MXene (Ti_3AlC_2), followed by MOFs their composites and derived structures. Whereas for ASC device AC based electrode was prepared as a negative electrode.

3.2.1 $Ti_3C_2T_x$ MXene Synthesis

MXene preparation was achieved by chemical etching of MAX phase. Here Ti_3AlC_2 powder was used as precursor. After carefully weighing 2 grams of MAX powder, it was gradually added in HF (48%). However, the addition of MAX to HF was slow but it took place in a controlled environment under vigorous stirring. The stirring was done in two phases before and after ultrasonication. The first phase of stirring carried out at constant RPM in an ice bath so that the temperature could be maintained. This helped in triggering the etching procedure which subsequently became instrumental in eliminating the Al portion. At the conclusion of first phase of stirring, for better exfoliation of sheets the solution was ultrasonicated for an hour this helped in achieving exfoliated and delaminated MXene sheets. The ultrasonication was followed by another spell of 24 hours with vigorous stirring. Obtained solution was washed with DI water at 6000 RPM in the centrifuge until the pH was neutralized (J. Luo et al., 2020). Finally fine powder of $Ti_3C_2T_x$ MXene was filtered and then dried out at ambient temperature for 24 hours. Real pictures from the experiment of MXene synthesis are shown in Fig. 3.1. Fig. 3.1 (a) and (b) show MAX phase Ti_3AlC_2 being stirred vigorously in HF. This phase was carried out carefully in the fume hood. The pH of the obtained solution was neutralized using thorough cleaning with DI water shown in Fig. 3.1(c). Fig.3.1(d) shows the obtained powder of MXene.

Figure 3.1 Complete synthesis procedure of MXene in real time photographic sequence

3.2.2 Synthesis of Co MOF and derived CoS

Preparation of CoS was undertaken in two steps, firstly Co MOF was synthesized which was then converted to CoS. To prepare Co MOF typical, MOF synthesis route was opted. To source Co, ~0.35 g of $\text{Co}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ salt mixed with 15ml solvent Dimethylformamide named as solution S1. The S1 was ultrasonicated for 15 minutes, so that it could dissolve easily. Another parallel solution (S2) was made where 0.2g of 2-methylimidazol an organic linker was dissolved in 15 ml of DMF. This solution S2 was then slowly and periodically added to S1 dropwise, with the help of a dropper.

The obtained mixture was then left for stirring at ambient conditions for 30 minutes at constant RPM. The solution was taken to stainless steel autoclaves walled with Teflon in the presence of NF inclined at an angle of 45° approximately and taken to oven for 24 hrs at 140°C . The purpose of keeping NF inclined at certain angle is to have the maximum growth of active material on the substrate. Since optimum growth of active material is vital therefore inclination of NF should be carried out very carefully in the vessel. Once the solution cooled to ambient environment, autoclave was taken out of the oven. The as prepared Co-MOF rinsed in absolute ethanol and powdered Co-MOF was dried out at 60°C for 24 hr, this concluded this first step of synthesis.

In step two the powdered Co MOF was mixed in 30 ml of sodium sulfide nonahydrate ($\text{Na}_2\text{S}\cdot 9\text{H}_2\text{O}$) solution, to have a better mix the solution underwent stirring for 15 minutes. The prepared mixture was transferred to Teflon walled stainless steel autoclave. The autoclave was taken to oven and kept at 140°C for 12hr. CoS powder was successfully obtained after 12 hours, and kept for the next step of electrode development, which will be discussed later.

3.2.3 Synthesis of FeCu MOF

The synthesis route for FeCu MOF was kept quite similar to that of Co MOF. Since bi-metallic MOF was intended therefore two different salts were used to source Fe and Cu. For Cu, 3.33mM of $\text{Cu}(\text{NO}_3)_2\cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$, whereas for Fe 6.67mM of iron chloride hexahydrate $\text{FeCl}_3\cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ were carefully weighed. Both salts were added to DMF one by one slowly and gradually to obtain a better mix which is (S1).

Another solution S2 was prepared simultaneously where an 5mM of 2 H_2BDC as an organic linker was mixed in 30ml of DMF. S2 was mixed with S1 slowly and gradually with a dropper while the S1 was on stirring. At constant RPM the prepared solution went through stirring for 15 minutes. Following the stirring process, the solution was

kept in autoclave with Teflon lining for 16hr at 120°C. After 16hr autoclave was cooled to ambient conditions and obtained FeCu MOF was rinsed and washed with ethanol. Fine powder was dried at 60°C for 24hr (Kulandaivel et al., 2022). As obtained fine powder of FeCu MOF was obtained ready to be incorporated with MXene to develop composite electrode which is discussed later in detail.

3.2.4 Synthesis of Fe MOF

The synthesis procedure for Fe MOF remains quite synonymous to the MOFs that we prepared earlier. Iron chloride hexahydrate ($\text{FeCl}_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$) precursor salt was used with approximately ~0.5 g of weight. The initial salt was slowly added to 15ml DMF and stirred thoroughly at constant RPM to obtain a well-mixed solution S1. Another solution S2 was prepared simultaneously, where ~0.3 g of H_2BDC was mixed with 15ml DMF, both the solutions were stirred to obtain homogeneous solutions.

Once the solutions are ready, S2 was slowly added to S1 with dropper, stirring was continuously in place. After both the solutions were mixed, the prepared mixture was left for stirring at ambient conditions for 15 minutes at constant RPM. Obtained solution was moved to oven in a sealed autoclave walled with Teflon, for 12 hrs at 140° C. At the conclusion of 12 hrs, the autoclave was allowed to cool down to room temperature and obtained Fe MOF powder was washed with ethanol and dried at 60°C for 24hrs.

3.3 Electrode development

In this section the electrode development is well concluded in detail. In the continuity of previous section where we discussed electrode material synthesis, here synthesis of composite materials and electrode growth is thoroughly unfolded. Obtained electrodes were MXene-CoS, stand-alone CoS, MXene-FeCu MOF, stand-alone FeCu MOF and AC (negative).

3.3.1 Synthesis of MXene-CoS electrode

After the successful individual synthesis of CoS and MXene, both materials were dissolved in 30 ml DMF with 2:1. Which means 25mg of MXene and 50mg of CoS were carefully weighed and dissolved in DMF with the help of magnetic stirrer. The stirring took place at ambient conditions, constant RPM for 15 minutes. At the conclusion of this stirring the obtained solution was taken to the autoclave with already immersed Ni foam (NF) inside the Teflon vessel. The NF before being kept was taken through a procedure called pretreatment, which is mentioned at the end of this section. The reaction was taken to the oven where it was placed at 140°C for 12hr. When autoclave was normalized to room temperature the NF with the grown material was carefully taken and gently washed out with absolute ethanol so that unnecessary mass load could be removed from the surface. NF was later dried at 60°C for 12 hours in vacuum so as the powered MXene-CoS leftover. A complete schematic of the development of MXene-CoS@NF experiment is expressed in Fig. 3.2. To establish the successful development of as prepared MXene-CoS, multiple characterizations have been carried out that are discussed in Chapter 4.

Figure 3.2 Schematic of development of MXene-CoS electrode

3.3.2 Synthesis of MXene-FeCu MOF electrode

To prepare MXene-FeCu MOF electrode, powdered FeCu MOF and MXene were mixed with a ratio of 2:1 in DMF. At constant RPM the solution was stirred for few minutes. Later the prepared solution was taken to autoclave and kept in oven for 16 hours at 140°C . The Teflon vessel in autoclave had a pretreated porous NF in it. Autoclave was taken out of the oven after it cooled down, and obtained NF with the grown material was washed with absolute ethanol to remove unwanted mass load. NF and as prepared MXene-FeCu MOF powder were dried in vacuum oven at 60°C for 12 hours. Complete electrode development of MXene-FeCu-MOF@NF is expressed in Fig. 3.3.

Figure 3.3 Schematic depiction of MXene-FeCu MOF@NF

3.3.3 Synthesis of MXene-Fe MOF electrode

As prepared Fe MOF and MXene powders were mixed to prepare MXene-Fe MOF composite and subsequent growth over NF. Both Fe MOF and MXene were mixed with a ratio of 2:1 in DMF. The solution was stirred at constant RPM for 15 minutes before it was transferred to oven. At the conclusion of 15 minutes stirring the obtained solution was poured in Teflon vessel and sealed in stainless steel autoclave where it was kept for 16 hours at 140°C. It is also to be noted that, the NF was already placed in an inclined posture within the Teflon vessel. The sealed system was cooled down to ambient conditions after 16 hours. NF with grown material and MXene-Fe MOF powder were washed and dried in vacuum oven at 60°C for 12 hours. Complete electrode development of MXene-Fe-MOF@NF is expressed in Fig. 3.4.

Figure 3.4 Schematic depiction of MXene-Fe MOF@NF

3.3.3 Synthesis procedure of negative electrode Activated Carbon (AC)

To prepare ASC appropriate negative electrode is of vital importance. The anode is prepared by carefully mixing three constituents such as AC, carbon black and PVDF. The synthesis started by making slurry with mass ratio kept as 80:10:10 for AC, carbon black and PVDF respectively. The ink also known as slurry was made by dropping ethanol dropwise. NF coated by the slurry worked as an anode.

Electrolyte gel composed of PVA-KOH was made according to the below mentioned procedure: Initially carefully weighed 6 grams of PVA mixed in 30 ml of DI water at 80 °C under stirring so that the transparent solution gets formed. The obtained gel was allowed to cool at ambient temperature naturally. Subsequently, 20 ml of 1 M KOH aqueous solution was added to the cooled gel under which is continuously being stirred so that the transparent, viscous solution is obtained. The transparent solution was transformed into a thin layer to be used as separator between ASC electrodes.

3.3.4 Pretreatment of Ni foam (NF)

Commercially available laboratory use NF with high porosity was procured. Small pieces or flakes were precisely cut with dimensions (5*10)mm so that they could be fit within the Teflon vessel. Since it is of vital importance that NF must be pretreated before use, therefore a three-step procedural protocol was undertaken. First of all, NF pieces were soaked into 3M HCl and ultrasonicated for 15 minutes. This step was followed by another 15 minutes of ultrasonication, but this time NF flakes were soaked in DI water. In third and the last step of the treatment, the flakes were soaked in absolute ethanol, and kept for another spell of ultrasonication of 15 minutes. It is highly recommended that freshly treated NF should be used before the onset of any experiment. After completing these three steps NF flakes were all set to be used as substrate, but before that they were properly dried with inert gas blow drying.

3.3.5 Synthesis of Electrolyte

Using appropriate electrolyte is very important to assemble a SS-ASC. PVA, KOH, DI water were used to prepare the electrolyte. Synthesis procedure for PVA-KOH gel electrolyte started by dissolving 6 g of PVA in 30 ml of DI water under heating at 80 °C with continuous stirring until the formation of clear transparent gel solution. The gel solution was allowed to cool at ambient temperature naturally. Subsequently, 20 mL of 1 M KOH aqueous solution was dropped into the cooled gel solution under continuous stirring until the formation of transparent, viscous solution.

Discussion

All the active electrodes were successfully synthesized using hydrothermal method, in addition to that AC based negative electrode was prepared for ASC device. Three sets of each electrode were prepared to have establish the reliability of the work. However, the growth of the active material was quite visible over the NF substrate, yet it is very

important to evaluate using various characterization tools to verify the achievement of the desired SC electrodes.

Chapter 4. Chemical Characterization

In this chapter all the chemical characterizations are thoroughly discussed. After the synthesis of all the materials, it is very important to verify the successful synthesis by conducting standard characterization tests. Therefore, a variety of characterization tools have been utilized to analyze, chemical composition, chemical bonding, morphology, crystallography, and chemical states of the obtained materials.

For crystallographic studies Bruker D8 Advance X-ray diffraction XRD was utilized with 2.2kW Cu anode as source for Xray with LYNXEYE detectors. The parameters for XRD were set with an increment of 0.03° at a scan rate of 0.3S. FEI FESEM and Jeol JEM-2100F TEM with ZrO/W (100) emitter were used to establish morphological studies and for elemental analysis EDS with AZtec analysis software was used. X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) Nexsa G2, ThermoScientific was utilized to carry out XPS studies, with monochromated, microfocused, low power Al K-Alpha source and hemispherical analyzer with 128-channel detector. Most of the characterizations were achieved using powder form of samples.

4.1 Field-emission Scanning electron Microscopy (FESEM)

The Ultra-high-resolution imaging of various nanostructures from 0.6nm to 1.2nm can be achieved by using a field emission scanning electron microscope (FE-SEM) at low accelerating voltages and close working distances. Multiple detectors are fitted into this system to collect a variety of signals, including secondary electron detectors (SE) for topographic data and back-scattered electron detectors (BSE) for imaging compositional contrast. Wavelength dispersive x-ray spectroscopy fitted with FE-SEM (WDS) can do elemental mapping more precisely than EDX with the

detection resolution of 2-20 eV and 30-300 ppm range coupled with FE-SEM (Brodusch et al., 2018). The conventional SEM is based upon heated tungsten filament for electron beam emission known as thermionic emitter. The economically feasible thermionic electron gun generates electron beam of size 4-8 nm. Such beam current produce insignificant brightness and causes the evaporation of filament known as thermal drift thus limiting the picture quality particularly at high-resolution. However, to obtain high-resolution image and applicable over a wide variety of materials such as thin samples as well as non-conductive samples without any pre-treatment, the field emission electron gun (FEG) is highly suggested such SEM is known as field emission scanning electron microscope (FESEM). The gun tip is mounted closer to anode at +2-6 kV, and generates $\sim 10^{10}$ fields of V/m near its surface. The sharp tip is beneficial for electron tunneling through the barrier into the vacuum with narrow beam size of (~ 2 nm). The electron beam column in FESEM consists of FEG and electromagnetic lenses as shown in Fig. 4.1. The design of this column is kept suitable for narrow probe size to achieve high resolution imaging. The low energy spread of FEG around 0.35 eV in comparison of 1.5 eV for thermionic emitter and with probe current within the range of 3 pA to 100 nA can provide high resolution imaging (Cik et al., 2015). The reduced electron probe size has been attained through a series of electromagnetic lenses called condenser and objective lens.

Figure 4.1 The electron optic column design for SEM (Cik et al., 2015).

4.1.1 MXene

For structural and morphological studies FESEM was utilized. In the Fig. 4.1 FESEM image of MXene is displayed. It is obvious from the image that, exfoliated MXene sheets have been achieved. However, the precursor Ti_3AlC_2 exhibits layered structure, but it is very important to investigate the morphological changes that take place after etching process. The Ti_3AlC_2 precursor was etched using HF, and Al content was extracted from the precursor. Resultantly $Ti_3C_2T_x$ MXene flakes were produced with multilayered sheet structure. The production of delaminated sheets is very important, as it provides more stability to the material, Fig. 4.2 also expresses delaminated layered structure. The exhibition of multilayer sheet structure verifies the successful synthesis of MXene sheets. Thin sheets at an average separation rate of 25 to 30 nm were obtained.

Figure 4.2 SEM image of as prepared MXene depicting delaminated sheet structure

4.1.2 MXene-CoS@NF

After the synthesis of active electrode material MXene-CoS, it is highly imperative to establish its morphological results. Therefore, MXene-CoS@NF was investigated in FESEM for morphological as well as structural studies. Fig. 4.3(a) and (b) represent low and high resolution images of MXene-CoS@NF respectively. The aim was to obtain a uniform growth of MXene-CoS on the NF, and it is quite evident from a high-resolution image in Fig. 4.3(a) that a uniform growth was observed over the NF. In contiguous image, Fig. 4.3(b) a high-resolution image of NF is shown, where MXene-CoS is grown over a magnified portion of NF. The proportionate mass load over NF proves the success of experiment which eventually resulted in achieving high performance of SC electrode.

Figure 4.3 (a) Low resolution image of MXene-CoS@NF, (b) High resolution image of MXene-CoS@NF

In Fig. 4.4 a detailed morphological image of MXene-CoS is expressed as well as in a contiguous image EDS analysis is expressed. Fig. 4.4(a) reveals CoS crystals and MXene sheets are successfully incorporated. CoS crystals can be seen settling between the MXene sheets filling the gaps, this diffusion eventually helped in shortening the gaps and consequently supporting ion electron transportation (J. Zhu et al., 2016). Moreover, this settlement of CoS within the gaps, prevented MXene sheets from restacking and thus increasing stability of active material. The spherical morphology of CoS is also helpful to catalyze redox reaction and enhance ion electron pathways

(W. Liu et al., 2015). The EDS analysis expressed in Fig. 4.4(b) show the high purity of obtained material, there is no contamination of external agent is found.

Figure 4.4 (a) FESEM image of MXene-CoS forming composite (b) EDS analysis of the obtained MXene-CoS@NF

4.1.3 MXene-FeCu MOF @NF

Morphological studies of MXene-FeCu MOF@NF were undertaken with the help of FESEM. In Fig. 4.5(a) and (b) low-resolution and high-resolution image of MXene-FeCu MOF@NF is shown. The results reveal the substantive growth of active material over NF surface. In Fig. 4.5(a) a low resolution image reveals uniformity of mass load spread over the surface, the 3d porous network of NF is well coated by the active material. In Fig. 4.5(b) a high resolution image of NF is expressed which further verifies ample mass load is grown over the porous network. Therefore, at first step of this study it is revealed that the mass load is uniformly distributed, and active material is grown over the porous network of NF.

Figure 4.5 (a) Low resolution image of MXene-FeCu MOF @NF (b) High resolution image of MXene-FeCu MOF @NF

To further investigate the morphology and structure of the composite, a detailed analysis was carried out. In Fig. 4.6 detail structural image and EDS analysis is expressed. Fig. 4.6(a) depicts that FeCu MOF crystals settling between the gaps of delaminated MXene sheets. Since FESEM also helps to calculate the particle or crystal size of the materials. Therefore, average crystal size calculated by FESEM turned out to be 25nm, with some crystals well over 30nm. The integration of these crystals over and between the MXene flakes will prevent restacking of sheets and culminate the process of crushing. Hence, a stable composite electrode material was obtained. In Fig. 4.6(b) EDS analysis is displayed, the analysis show that no impurity was found in the composite and all the constituents of the composite materials were found with respective concentration.

Figure 4.6(a) High magnification image of MXene-FeCu MOF@NF (b) EDS analysis of MXene-FeCu MOF

4.1.4 MXene-Fe MOF @NF

FESEM was used to carry out morphological studies for MXene-Fe MOF@NF. A high resolution image is shown in Fig. 4.7(a) with uniform growth of MXene-Fe MOF over NF. The results show that significant growth of active material was observed, with excellent mass load. A high resolution image is shown in Fig. 4.7(b), which further verifies the growth of active material over NF. These results prove the authenticity of the synthesis process, with successful growth of active material with in-situ growth.

Figure 4.7 (a) Low resolution image of MXene-Fe MOF@NF (b) High resolution image of MXene-Fe MOF@NF

In depth morphological investigation was carried out to further reveal the structure and morphology of as prepared composite. High magnification image of MXene-Fe MOF is shown in Fig. 4.8(a). It is evident from the image, Fe MOF crystals successfully settled between the gaps of MXene flakes, moreover MOF crystals can also be seen spread over MXene sheets. This interlocking of MXene sheets and MOF crystals is further explained in TEM investigations where a clear image displays morphological traits of the composite. Fig. 4.8(b) shows EDS analysis of the as prepared composite material. EDS results shown high purity of the obtained material is achieved, all the

constituents have been identified and no impurity material is observed. This marks the achievement of high purity of the composite as well as desired morphology is obtained.

Figure 4.8 (a) High magnification image of MXene-Fe MOF (b) EDS analysis of MXene-Fe MOF

4.2 High resolution transmission electron Microscopy (HRTEM)

For the detailed morphological studies, HRTEM was used along with SAED. HRTEM images helped to understanding the in depth knowledge of the structure of active electrode materials as well as lattice spacing. Moreover, SAED helped in evaluating the crystallinity, lattice parameters and crystal structure of the active material.

A strong method for examining the internal structure of the nanoparticles is the transmission electron microscope (TEM). The shape, surface structure, particle size,

and wall thickness of nanostructures have all been well-studied through TEM at a resolution of nearly 0.4nm (Franken et al., 2020). In TEM an electron beam of uniform current density within the energy range of 60 to 150 keV) is focused on a thin sample with the help of condenser as shown in Fig. 4.9. The interaction of electron beam with the sample, generates variety of electron signal such as transmitted electrons, elastically or inelastically scattered. Such interaction of electron with the sample surface is affected by several factors involving size, density and elemental composition. The intensity of transmitted electrons is greatly influenced by the electron density of the sample in a way that higher electron densities produce low signal of transmitted electrons and vice versa for low electron density region (Wiktor et al., 2017). Thus, the region with varying electron density results into different brightness. However, this technique involves heavy sample preparation which transform it into a time-consuming and costly approach. Moreover, structural variations in samples may occur during the sample preparation for instance agglomeration of particles in colloidal suspension.

Figure 4.9 Schematic diagram of TEM and principle of image formation (Z. L. Wang, 2003)

For the investigation of crystal structure of NPs, SAED is another crucial microscopy technique. For this purpose, electrons are energized to a specific wavelength through an electrostatic potential in order to interact with the sample under observation. In a crystalline sample, the periodic framework of crystallites acts diffracts the electrons in a predictable manner. The obtained diffraction pattern provides significant information about the crystallographic features of the sample. Nevertheless, some limitations are associated with SAED technique such as contribution of large number of particles to the diffraction pattern due to large size of illuminated region, devising their individual study difficult. However, in modern ‘nano-diffraction’ technique, the illuminated area of the sample is kept small by using the electron probe size of 0.1 nm with the aid of field emission TEM (Ponce et al., 2021).

4.2.1 MXene-CoS

In Fig. 4.10 TEM, HRTEM along with SAED images are displayed. TEM image of as prepared MXene-CoS in Fig.4.10(a) unfold further details of its structure. The darker portion shows CoS whereas the lighter portion of the image depicts MXene sheets. Both MXene and CoS are successfully incorporated in a composite formation, which is in agreement of the FESEM investigation discussed earlier. Moreover, in a contiguous image in Fig. 4.10(b) HRTEM image with high crystallinity of the materials is displayed with typical lattice fringes. Lattice parameters of ~ 0.2 nm and ~ 1.3 nm well-matched with planes (400) and (002) of crystalline MXene-CoS. The inset in Fig. 4.10(b) is selected area electron diffraction (SAED) that reveals hexagonal lattice formation is attributed to MXene flakes whereas the formation of diffraction rings is associated with CoS crystals.

Figure 4.10 (a) TEM image of MXene-CoS (b)HRTEM image of MXene-CoS with SAED inset

4.2.2 MXene-FeCu MOF

In Fig. 4.11 TEM, HRTEM along with SAED images are displayed for MXene-FeCu MOF. TEM image of as prepared MXene-FeCu MOF is displayed in Fig. 4.11(a), the image verifies the composite formation. MXene flakes interlocked with MOF crystals can be seen, the darker area of the image shows presence of MOF crystals,

whereas MXene sheets manifested slightly lighter color. The TEM results further verify the FESEM findings, and composite formation. In a contiguous image represented in Fig. 4.11(b) HRTEM image is displayed, where visible lattice fringes are manifested corresponding to (002). Moreover, an inset in Fig. 4.11(b) representing SAED of the composite is shown that reveals crystallinity of the composite, with cubic structure due to ample presence of Fe and Cu.

Figure 4.11 (a) TEM image of MXene-FeCu MOF (b) HRTEM image of MXene-FeCu MOF with SAED inset

4.2.3 MXene-Fe MOF

In Fig. 4.12 TEM, HRTEM and SAED images are expressed in MXene-Fe MOF. In Fig. 4.12(a) TEM image of MXene-Fe MOF is shown, image verifies the distinct formation of MXene-Fe MOF composite. Here MXene sheets can be seen as darker area, whereas Fe MOF crystals can be seen in the periphery. MXene and Fe MOF crystals are interlocked, which compliments the FESEM findings. Interspacing between MXene sheets is filled with Fe MOF crystals. In Fig. 4.12(b) HRTEM image of the composite is shown, with visible lattice fringes associated to (002) and (104) planes of MXene-Fe MOF composite. SAED image is expressed in the inset, with diffraction rings associated to Fe MOF whereas overall hexagonal structure is attributed to MXene sheets.

Figure 4.12 (a) TEM image of MXene-Fe MOF (b) HRTEM image of MXene-Fe MOF with SAED inset

4.3 X-Ray diffraction (XRD)

The crystallography is an important aspect to determine the crystal structure of the materials, it helps in identification of the materials as well as composite formation.

The XRD was carried out on powder sample, for MXene alone, MXene-CoS, MXene-FeCu MOF and MXene-Fe MOF. The parameters kept for scan were set at an increment of 0.03° with scan rate of 0.3S.

Powder X-ray diffraction (XRD) is a popular method for characterizing materials at the nanoscale. The sample analysis in terms of Phase identification, sample purity, and crystallite size can be done through powder XRD which is a supplement to different microscopic and spectroscopic techniques. X-ray diffraction (XRD) is a key technique

for examining the structural details of nanomaterials since X-rays have atomic-scale wavelengths. Moreover, the strain states in thin films can also be studied through XRD since it provides unmatched accuracy in the measurement of atomic spacing. The four basic parts of a conventional powder XRD equipment are an X-ray source, specimen stage, receiving optics, and an X-ray detector. For powder or polycrystalline diffraction, the sample should possess a smooth, and levelled surface. For this purpose, the particles are usually ground up to 0.002 mm to 0.005 mm cross sections and then pressed into a specimen stage to have a smooth flat surface. The powder sample is well-homogenized with random distribution of crystallites (Bishnoi et al., 2017). The sample stage exists in the center of the focusing circle, while the source, detector, and related optics are situated around the edge of the circle as shown in Fig 4.13. The foundation of XRD analysis is based upon Bragg's law. This rule enables precise quantifications of experimental findings for the identification of crystal structures. The Bragg's angle, or the angle between the plane of the specimen and the X-ray source, is (θ) , whereas the angle between the projection of the X-ray and the detector is (2θ) .

Figure 4.13 A schematic of the experimental set-up of XRD (Das et al., 2014)

To resolve structural information of the crystal lattice through XRD, the material is exposed to a monochromatic X-ray beam since the materials are made up of several repeated uniform atomic units known as crystals. Fundamentally, polychromatic X-rays are generated in cathode-ray tubes under vacuum which are subsequently filtered through a monochromator to produce monochromatic radiation. The monochromatic X-rays are then focused on the sample surface and get diffracted from the atomic planes of the sample in accordance with Bragg's Law (Das et al., 2014).

$$2d\sin\theta = n\lambda$$

Here, n represents an integer determining the order of diffraction, λ signifies the wavelength of incident X-ray beam, d shows the inter atomic planes spacing, and θ representing the angle of incidence X-rays.

Figure 4.14 The fundamentals of X-Ray Diffractogram and Bragg's law (Bishnoi et al., 2017)

In X-Ray diffraction pattern, the intensity of diffracted X-ray beam is plotted against the diffraction angle 2θ as shown in Fig. 4.14. The XRD analysis of a sample initiates by indexing the XRD peaks that is assigning the appropriate Miller indices to each peak of the diffraction pattern. The XRD peaks of a diffraction pattern can be indexed in three ways, (i) matching the observed XRD pattern against the reference data set (JCPDS-cards) (ii) analytical techniques (iii) graphical approach. The atomic configurations at interfaces may be precisely and quantitatively determined by measuring the intensities using XRD (L. Zhang et al., 2020). The XRD peaks expand

as the size of the crystallite shrinks from bulk to nanoscale dimensions. The Scherrer equation $D = k\lambda/\beta\cos\theta$ supports the peak broadening at a particular diffraction angle (theta) due to reduction of crystallite size (D) by enhancing the full-width half maximum (β) (Nanoparticles: Properties, applications and toxicities). The typical value of Scherrer constant k , is 0.91, the constant (λ) is the value of employed X-ray wavelength. For the calculation of crystallite size through Scherrer equation, the diffraction angle is calculated in radians and corresponds to θ instead of 2θ (Nanoparticles: Properties, applications and toxicities).

Figure 4.15 A Typical XRD pattern (Das et al., 2014)

It is crucial to take into account the limitations of standard laboratory X-ray diffractometer in terms of detection and quantification (Holder & Schaak, 2019). Although XRD is a significant characterizing tool for the identification of crystalline phases in a sample, however, the amorphous materials with lack long-range crystallographic ordering, do not create patterns with distinguish diffraction peaks. Moreover, XRD pattern of a sample containing impurity phases of an amorphous component, along with nanoscale crystalline components, may appear the identical to

the pattern of a sample composed of only nanocrystalline component(s). XRD patterns of amorphous phases can be considered the same in terms of peak broadening as those for nanoparticles of dimensions lesser than 2 nm. The low-intense peaks, corresponding to impurities are hard to observe. Thus, additional characterizing techniques are essentially required to ensure the purity and crystallinity level of the synthesized material.

4.3.1 MXene-CoS

A comparison of XRD results of MXene (red) and MXene-CoS (black) is displayed in Fig. 4.16. The range for the scan was kept from 5° to 80° , so that a complete scan can be obtained. After the exfoliation of Al content, the prominent characteristic peaks at 8.6° , 18.2° , and 27.7° correspond to (002), (004), and (006) planes. The exfoliation also caused a peak shift towards the lower angles which is due to the formation of -F, -OH, and -O functional groups. Moreover, two peaks at 25.3° and 27.7° correspond to anatase and rutile phases TiO_2 which shows high quality of obtained MXene (Adil et al., 2023). The characteristic XRD peaks for MXene-CoS were observed at 8.6° , 18.6° , 25.3° , 39.9° , 47° and 55° . In this pattern the peaks found at 39.9° , 47° and 55° can be attributed to planes (211), (220) and (311) planes respectively (T. Hu et al., 2015). The XRD pattern further proves the phase purity and quality of the composite.

Figure 4.16 XRD pattern of MXene and MXene-CoS

4.3.2 MXene-FeCu MOF

The XRD scan for MXene and MXene-FeCu MOF were carried out on powder sample and expressed in Fig. 4.17. Since XRD for MXene has already been discussed above, therefore in this section XRD for MXene-FeCu MOF is discussed. The peaks for MXene-FeCu MOF composite were observed at 38°, 48° and 64° which are attributed to (110), (220) and (200) planes respectively.

Figure 4.17 XRD pattern of MXene and MXene-FeCu MOF

4.3.3 MXene-Fe MOF

XRD for MXene-Fe MOF composite was carried out on powder sample. A comparison of MXene alone and MXene-Fe MOF composite is shown in Fig. 4.18. XRD results show the successful formation of the desired composite, with high crystallinity and phase purity. Less intensified Fe MOF characteristic peaks were observed at $\sim 13^\circ$, $\sim 33^\circ$, and $\sim 52.5^\circ$ attributed to (200), (104) and (116) planes respectively.

Figure 4.18 XRD scan for MXene and MXene-Fe MOF

4.4 X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS)

In this section XPS is discussed for active composite materials. Chemical states and composition of obtained materials were determined using XPS. The XPS was carried out only on as prepared active electrode materials such as MXene-CoS and MXene-FeCu MOF. Powder form of samples was used to carry out scan.

X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) is an effective characterization approach for surface (< 10 nm) chemical analysis in terms of electronic structure, elemental composition and oxidation states of elements in a material (Krishna & Philip, 2022a). The most crucial area of a solid substance is its surface because it regulates the material interaction with its surroundings therefore analyzing the material surfaces is crucial. The surface of a material is fundamentally a material defect with perturbed atomic periodicity causing considerable changes in structural, electronic and vibrational states

at the atomic level to make surface highly reactive towards the environment. Surface adsorption usually occurs at sub-monolayer ($\sim A^0$) whereas surface modification processes affect the underlying surface up to several microns (Krishna & Philip, 2022a). Such chemical functionalization of a material surface greatly alters the surface properties such as interaction of surface with the environment. Consequently, there is a growing need to understand the material surface characteristics, such as surface chemistry, morphology, and crystallography (phase composition) to create more effective catalysts (Mourdikoudis et al., 2018).

Theory of XPS

The XPS is a UHV method in which the material being studied is subjected to X-rays. Photoelectrons ejected from the various electronic level of material's surface are then detected by a hemispherical analyzer to calculate their kinetic energy (KE). The change in binding energy (BE) of an electron is referred as the chemical shift in terms of varying oxidation state or restructured electronic charge distribution around the nucleus because of varying chemical bonding of an element with its surrounding environment. The BE of an energy level can be estimated from the measured KE of the photoelectron derived as provided in eq below (Krishna & Philip, 2022b).

$$E_B = h\nu - E_K - \phi$$

In the given expression E_K refers to the kinetic energy, E_B is the binding energy, h is the Plank's constant, ν is the frequency of X-rays, and ϕ is the work function. Fig. 4.19 representing the schematics of XPS theory involving the X-rays interaction with the specimen atoms.

Figure 4.19 Schematic representation of XPS theory by using energy level diagram (Krishna & Philip, 2022b)

XPS significantly probes the quantitative chemical composition of the material surface within 10 nm range with good sensitivity in the range of 0.1-1 at.% for all the elements excluding H and He. The XPS spectrum intended for identifying the elements on a material surface is known as ‘survey’ or ‘wide scan’, in which the intensity is measured in counts per second and plotted against binding energies (eV) of e_s^- . The spectrum also involves various peaks associated with photoelectrons and Auger electrons other than the inelastically scattered e_s^- contributing in the background signal (Krishna & Philip, 2022b). Generally, the photoelectron peaks are relatively less complex, narrower and with greater intensities comparative to Auger peaks.

To anticipate the chemical composition of a surface the core level peaks are of significant importance. Basically, the core levels of an atom are greatly influenced by the electronic charge distribution around the nucleus. Upon the combination of two atoms, the charge transfer occur in the valence bands of both the atoms through partial (covalent bonding) or complete (in ionic bond). The extent of the charge transfer is associated with the relative difference of electronegativities of the bonded atoms

(Krishna & Philip, 2022b). Therefore, ion holding effective positive charge with less electron screening effect at its core levels possess greater binding energies than an electronegative ion due to the increased screening effects.

However, in case of insulating samples the surface charging effects may contribute to the peak shift, broadening and asymmetric causing a complex or inaccurate analysis (Mourdikoudis et al., 2018).

4.4.1 MXene-CoS

A complete XPS survey spectra of MXene-CoS is shown in Fig. 4.20. Very high purity of obtained material is achieved which agrees with XRD and FESEM investigations. XPS results mark the presence of all the constituents of the composite such as Ti-2p with characteristic peaks at ~456, ~459, ~461.4 and ~464.8 eV are attributed to Ti-C ($2p_{3/2}$), Ti-O ($2p_{3/2}$), Ti-C ($2p_{1/2}$) and Ti-O ($2p_{1/2}$) respectively. Co 2p XPS spectra is deconvoluted into two peaks display $2p_{3/2}$ electronic configurations at 781.3 eV and ~778.8 eV and $2p_{1/2}$ electronic configuration at 797.1 eV. A couple of satellite peaks could be observed at ~786 eV and ~803 eV reflecting the Co^{2+} ion.

Characteristic peaks for C-1s found at ~284.6, ~288.1 and ~282 eV belong to C-C, C-O and Ti-C respectively. In XPS spectra for S-2p the spin-orbit peaks at ~162.6 eV correspond to S $2p_{3/2}$. Moreover, peaks observed at ~161 eV, and ~164 eV belong to Co-S, and S $2p_{1/2}$ respectively, whereas peak at ~170 eV is satellite peak (Fantauzzi et al., 2015).

Figure 4.20 XPS spectra of MXene-CoS

4.4.2 MXene-FeCu MOF

XPS spectra for MXene-FeCu MOF is displayed in Fig. 4.21. The overall spectra marked the presence of Fe, Cu, C, and Ti, their chemical states and composition. In this spectrum Ti-2p peaks are spotted at ~ 456 , ~ 459 , ~ 464.7 eV correspond to Ti-C ($2p_{3/2}$), Ti-O ($2p_{3/2}$), and Ti-O ($2p_{1/2}$) respectively. Whereas the peaks for C-1s seen at ~ 282 and ~ 284.6 eV are related to Ti-C and C-C respectively. Cu-2p peaks observed at ~ 934.5 eV which belongs to Cu $2p_{3/2}$ whereas another peak at ~ 954.4 eV corresponds to Cu $2p_{1/2}$. A set of satellite peaks is also observed at ~ 962.9 eV, and ~ 943.1 eV. For Fe 2p, peaks at ~ 711.5 and ~ 716.2 eV can be attributed to Fe $2p_{3/2}$ and peaks at ~ 724.8 and ~ 728.9 correspond to Fe $2p_{1/2}$.

Figure 4.21 XPS Spectra of MXene-FeCu MOF

4.4.3 MXene-Fe MOF

MXene-Fe MOF XPS is expressed in Fig. 4.22. The survey spectrum confirms the presence of all the constituents of the composite like Ti, Fe and Cu with high purity of the active material and establishing their chemical states and composition. In this spectrum the peaks for C-1s observed at ~ 282 and ~ 284.6 eV are related to Ti-C and C-C respectively. Ti-2p peaks are spotted at ~ 456 , ~ 459 , ~ 464.7 eV correspond to Ti-C ($2p_{3/2}$), Ti-O ($2p_{3/2}$), and Ti-O ($2p_{1/2}$) respectively. Fe 2p, peaks spotted at ~ 711.5 and ~ 716.2 eV are associated to Fe $2p_{3/2}$ whereas peaks at ~ 724.8 and ~ 728.9 correspond to Fe $2p_{1/2}$.

Figure 4.22 XPS Spectra of MXene-Fe MOF

This concludes our discussion of Chemical characterization; all the chemicals were characterized using various equipment. Their structure, chemical composition, crystallography, and elemental analysis were conducted. All the results, state that high purity of the obtained materials was achieved. No impurity was found, the goals for achieving certain morphology and structure have been achieved which verifies the authenticity and credibility of synthesis procedure and obtained materials.

Discussion

All the materials were analyzed by using sophisticated characterization equipment. The characterizations were carried out on powder samples, obtained during electrode material synthesis. High quality materials were synthesized, XRD, XPS and EDS analysis shown that the as prepared materials were pure, and no contamination was

observed. Structural and morphological studies reveal that the desired morphology and structure was achieved, as was aimed in the first chapter, which means that as prepared electrodes are capable to be tested electrochemically and evaluated.

Chapter 5. Electrochemical testing and evaluation

In this chapter electrochemical studies are discussed. Electrochemical (EC) evaluation of electrode materials is of paramount importance for any energy storage application. Biologic 200 workstation was used to study electrochemistry of as prepared electrodes and asymmetric supercapacitors (ASC) device. As prepared electrodes were individually tested in a three electrode setup, with Pt foil counter electrode and 2 M KOH electrolyte. Various electrochemical tests have been carried out to establish EC performance such as, cyclic voltammetry (CV), galvanostatic charge discharge (GCD) and electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS).

After analyzing EC performance of individual electrodes, asymmetric supercapacitor devices (ASC) were prepared. In ASCs MXene-Cos, MXene-FeCu MOF and MXene-Fe MOF were used as positive electrodes and AC based electrodes were used as negative electrode in ASCs.

a) Cyclic Voltammetry (CV)

CV is one of the most important measurements to evaluate electrochemical performance of any energy storage device. In CV output current is measured with input voltage sweep. It is useful to investigate potential dependent response of SCs more particularly CV is handy in studying electrochemical performance of pseudocapacitors.

In CV measurements current variation by applied potential and time is measured at fixed potential sweeps. Current depending on time and potential is calculated over a fixed potential window. The sweep rate S representing potential variation along with time (dv/dt) commonly represented as mV/S. The obtained output current direction is

subjected to the direction of sweep rate that changes periodically upon reaching a certain fixed potential value.

CV results are expressed in the form of graphs of i vs V . In Fig. 5.1 signature CV plots of EDLC, Pseudocapacitance and battery-type SC materials are displayed. In an ideal situation of SCs, their capacitance is not frequency dependent hence the amount of charge storage is proportionate to voltage. Hence in case of constant scan rate which is mV/S the current response also remains constant with specific CV behavior depending on the electrode material used. I vs V CV plots shown in Fig. 5.1 of EDLC, pseudocapacitive, and battery-type SCs manifest distinct electrochemical behavior. Since in EDLCs the reaction mechanism is non Faradic, and a charged double layer is created at electrode-electrolyte interaction thus it gives a rectangular shape instead of prominent redox peaks (Nguyen et al., 2021).

Contrary to that Faradic mechanism instigates redox reactions in Pseudocapacitive and battery-type materials. Reaction kinetics of different materials showing Faradic reactions, is the basis of identifying pseudocapacitive and battery-type materials. In pseudocapacitive materials, reaction mechanism is not diffusion-controlled restrained on surface of the electrode. As diffusion is not restricted, therefore the phase change during electrochemical polarization is unlikely to take place (Nguyen et al., 2021). Thus, a rectangular CV curve quite similar to that of EDLC is obtained. Whereas in battery-type diffusion controlled Faradic reactions take place leaving prominent redox peaks in CV curves as can be witnessed in Fig. 5.1.

Figure 5.1 CV plots of different types of SCs

b) Galvanostatic charge-discharge (GCD)

GCD is another most important measurement to evaluate any energy storage device. At a constant current density, a potential difference occurs that increases linearly with time meanwhile charge accumulates on the plates. In GCD the current is added or drawn from the system at a constant rate in the range of two cut-off limits, this range is normally called as operating potential window. Depending on the type of electrochemical reactions taking place during the process, different GCD profiles emerge for each specific material.

The GCD plots for EDLC show sharp slopy curves, whereas in pseudocapacitive materials it forms a semi plateau with slope trend. Battery-type materials possess a plateau shape during GCD cycles as shown in Fig. 5.2. There is a lot of information that can be calculated using GCD plots to evaluate SCs in terms of specific capacity, areal and volumetric capacities, energy, and power densities. These values are calculated using equations that are discussed in detail during electrochemical evaluation of as prepared electrodes and ASCs.

Figure 5.2 GCD plots of different types of SCs

c) Electrochemical Impedance Spectroscopy (EIS)

EIS is used to determine frequency dependent responses, capacitance, and resistance of SCs. Cell potential is subjected to sine wave over frequency and obtained response of alternating current is calculated. With the help of an equivalent circuit basic parameters of a SC electrode are declared, using impedance comparison with current response. It helps to indicate the capacitive behavior of single electrode as well as two or even more electrodes configuration of electrochemical devices. Generally, it is denoted as $Z(\omega)$ and can be calculated as below

$$Z(\omega) = V(t) / I(t) \quad (5.1)$$

This relation is analogous to Ohm's law, here $V(t) = V_0 \sin(\omega t)$ and $I(t) = I_0 \sin(\omega t + \phi)$ both V and I are time variant and are regulated on the frequency ω module. $Z(\omega)$ could include resistance (R), capacity (C) as well as inductive (L) elements. EIS is also helpful as it permits equivalent series resistance (ESR) and other resistance involved or attributed to SCs so that they could be isolated and quantified. ESR evaluation is also crucial as it helps to design SC device and to optimise power density. The data

obtained from the EIS can be interpreted in different ways, by drawing the equivalent circuits, or using analytical way to check frequency response or by making a hardware circuit simulation.

Widely used method is to fit the data generated from the response against applied frequency to the data collected from models of equivalent circuits. It is mandatory for an equivalent circuit to simulate the response of actual system, this circuit is composed of elements such as Ohmic resistance (R), capacitances C, or pseudocapacitance C_P and inductance L. Moreover, on the increase of diffusion impedance which is associated to porous electrodes or electrolytes another element called Warburg impedance W is added. Another method is to explain frequency response through analytical way, based on reaction kinetics coupled with double-layer capacitance. In addition to that, there is another method which is least used where hardware simulation is carried out and its EIS is compared with obtained results from the working electrode. In this study, the fitting of equivalent circuit is opted to interpret EIS results.

d) Cyclic Stability

Cyclic performance or cyclic stability is integral part of various electrochemical evaluations for any storage device. It is as important that on the basis of this evaluation scope of a certain material, electrode or device can be predicted. The cyclic stability is an extension of GCD, for longer time and cycles at a constant current density. The electrode or the device is assembled in a typical same way as it is done for CV, GCD or EIS. A constant current density is fixed, along with certain amount of successive GCD cycles that could be few thousands, meanwhile the operating potential window V remains same as was achieved for GCD.

Cyclic performance or stability tests can take few hours, or it can last up to few days, subject to number of successive given to the system, as well as value of current density.

The greater the value shorter will be the time. Capacity retention, cycle shape and operating potential window are the key elements that need to be calculated towards the end of the test. Once the stability test concludes, the capacity of successive GCD cycles is calculated in intervals using equation (eq) (5.5). Total number of cycles are divided into intervals, so that after every fifty or hundred cycles the capacity of the cycle is calculated up to last cycle. Hence an average capacity is calculated and written as capacity retention usually in percentage. It shows how much of the capacity is retained by the electrode or device after a certain number of GCD cycles. The results are expressed in the form of graph and an inset is attached to display first and last ten cycles of the test.

5.1 Electrochemical performance evaluation of MXene-CoS electrode

Electrochemical performance of MXene-CoS electrode started with cyclic voltammetry CV. In Fig. 5.3(a) CV of as prepared MXene-CoS electrode is shown, CV scans were undertaken at various scan rates form 5mV/S to 30mV/S. These scans were carried out in a three electrode configuration, where Pt was kept as counter electrode and Hg/HgO as reference electrode. CV scans revealed a typical battery-type behavior and exhibited deep redox sites (Brousse et al., 2015). The obtained potential 0.65V. Despite the change in scan rate, CV curves maintained a similar pattern with prominent redox peaks that proves high redox reversibility of MXene-CoS electrode. It is believed that possible reason behind this could be the nature of variation in different oxidation states of of Co^{2+} , Co^{3+} , and Co^{4+} (Ramachandran, Rajavel, et al., 2018). The exhibition of characteristic Faradic behavior with a couple of redox peaks reveals battery-type behavior of as prepared electrode. In addition to that, the marginal repositioning or shift of oxidation peaks towards positive as well as in a similar fashion slight displacement of reduction peaks is attributed to internal resistance of the material

(Bahaa et al., 2019) . Therefore, the possibility of Faradic redox reaction could be explained as under (B. Qu et al., 2012; J. Yang et al., 2017).

Figure 5.3 (a) CV graphs of MXene-CoS (b) CV comparison of MXene-CoS and CoS

Due to the electrode and electrolyte interaction in the process of oxidation and reduction the redox peaks manifested OH^- diffusion (Subramani et al., 2017). In

contiguous image in Fig.5.3(b) a CV comparison between MXene-CoS and bare CoS is shown at a scan rate of 30mV/s. On a similar scan rate, the EC performance of as prepared MXene-CoS electrode is much superior to that of bare CoS. This significant enhancement in CV graphs, testify the credibility of the composite material design and successful development of electrode. The performance enhancement can be reasoned by the occurrence of intercalation between MXene sheets and cations (K⁺), moreover functional groups associated with Ti₃C₂ also contributed to surface redox reaction hence possible EC reaction can be stated as below (H. Liu et al., 2020; Y. Tang et al., 2017).

The GCD graphs of as obtained MXene-CoS electrode are shown in Fig. 5.4(a), at a variety of current densities ranging from 3 to 30 mA cm⁻². The GCD plots reveal shape symmetry with a high redox activity. GCD curves achieved a potential window of 0.5 V. Moreover, the signature shape of battery-type material can be observed in GCD which is in continuity of the pattern that is observed in CV graphs. Discharging time of MXene-CoS electrode at a current density of 3mA cm⁻² remained ~400 S. In Fig. 5.4(b) areal and specific capacities of obtained electrode are presented, at the current density ranging from 3 to 30mA cm⁻². The capacities are calculated using the below mentioned equations (Bahaa et al., 2019).

$$C_{SC} = \frac{2I \times \int V dt}{mV} \quad (5.5)$$

$$C_{AC} = \frac{2I \times \int V dt}{SV} \quad (5.6)$$

Here eq (iv) C_{sc} shows specific capacity (C_{SC}, mAhg⁻¹), and C_{av} shows areal capacity of obtained electrode. Here “I” is discharging current, in “∫Vdt” is the area under the

discharging curve and m is the mass load of active material on the substrate. “S” is the active surface area and “V” is the potential window achieved in the GCD. The specific capacities of MXene-CoS electrode are $\sim 447, 388, 349, 327, 315, 296, 278, 272$ and 234 mAh g^{-1} with areal capacities of $\sim 1.78, 1.55, 1.39, 1.30, 1.26, 1.18, 1.12, 1.09$ and 0.93 mAh cm^{-2} at current densities of 3, 5, 8, 10, 12, 15, 18, 20 and 30 mA cm^{-2} , respectively.

Figure 5.4 (a) GCD graphs of MXene-CoS (b) Specific and areal capacities

The Electrochemical Impedance Spectroscopy (EIS) plots or Nyquist plots of MXene-CoS before and after stability tests are shown in Fig. 5.5(a) along with bare CoS electrode. EIS studies help to examine charge transfer resistance (R_{ct}), solution

solution resistance (R_s) as well as diffusion resistance (R_w) of the electrode. Nyquist plots are generally divided into low frequency region as well as high frequency regions. The curves at high frequency region correspond to series or solution resistance R_s of electrode. R_s is the combination of Ohmic and substrate resistances. The value of R_s for MXene-CoS electrode before cyclic stability was $\sim 0.7\Omega$ and after 5000 successive GCD cycles it became $\sim 0.9\Omega$. Solution resistance R_s for stand-alone CoS turned up to be $\sim 1.2\Omega$. The formation of semi-circle in high frequency region depicts contact resistance as well as contact capacitance between electrode material and NF. The larger diameter of semicircle gives higher values contact resistance and capacitance.

Charge transfer resistance R_{ct} for MXene-CoS before cyclic stability was $\sim 0.56\Omega$ which changed to $\sim 0.6\Omega$ after 5000 GCD cycles. In low frequency region the inclined line shows Warburg resistance (R_w) which is diffusion resistance happens at the interaction of electrolyte ion with the electrode. The levels of diffusion resistance can be predicted by the slopy path of inclined line. Here stand-alone CoS manifested much higher values of R_w than MXene-CoS electrode. In addition, as prepared MXene-CoS electrode withheld a straight and vertical projection in low frequency region showing lower values of diffusion resistance R_w . MXene-CoS manifested capacitive and conductive behavior with low values of solution resistance R_s , whereas stand-alone CoS displayed only conductive behavior (H. Liu et al., 2020). The equivalent circuit is drawn in the inset in Fig. 5.5(a).

Study of long time cyclic performance is very important to establish material and electrode stability of any energy storage device. As the stability tests help to understand whether the as prepared material can be scale up for commercial and industrial purposes or not. The cyclic stability of MXene-CoS is displayed in Fig.

5.5(b). The electrode was tested for 5000 successive GCD cycles with current density of $30\text{mA}/\text{cm}^2$. The calculated specific capacity after 5000 cycles retained up to 94% from the initial cycles. The last ten cycles of stability performance are shown in the inset in Fig. 5.5(b). There was no shape change observed after the conclusion of 5000 cycles, which shows as prepared MXene-CoS electrode holds tremendous material and electrode stability.

Figure 5.5 (a) EIS graph of MXene-CoS before and after stability along with bare CoS (b) Cyclic stability after 5000 successive GCD cycles

5.2 Electrochemical performance of MXene-CoS/AC ASC

Studying the electrochemical performance of as prepared electrode in a two electrode system is very important. Therefore, a solid state asymmetric supercapacitor (ASC) device was designed, with MXene-CoS electrode as positive and AC was kept as negative electrode. The device is termed as solid state due to all solid material involved in the design such as solid electrodes and a solid electrolyte membrane.

Cyclic voltammetry of as prepared MXene-CoS/AC ASC is shown in Fig. 5.6(a-b). In Fig. 5.6(a) CV graphs of ASC at varying potential window are shown at a constant scan rate 100mV/S. The range of potential window started from 0.8V to 1.6V. At potential window 0.8V and 0.9V no CV shape was seen, as well as characteristic oxidation and reduction peaks also remained missing. The characteristic oxidation and reduction peaks started developing from 1V, then with every increase in the potential window the peaks started getting more prominent in the shape till 1.6V. A complete set of oxidation and reduction peaks was achieved with battery type CV pattern at 1.6V of potential window. This proves that as prepared ASC has achieved a wide operational potential window which is significant for any storage device. In Fig. 5.6(b) CV plots of ASC at different scan rates from 5mV/S to 100mV/S are shown with 1.6V of potential window. With the increase in scan rate the current density also increased, while keeping the CV shape intact. All the CV graphs displayed a couple of redox peaks associated to both electrodes of ASC, which verifies the occurrence of Faradic reactions between the electrodes.

Figure 5.6 (a) CV curves of ASC with varying potential window at constant scan rate (b) CV curves of ASC

In Fig. 5.7(a) GCD plots of ASC are shown, the range of current density to execute GCD was kept from $2\text{mA}/\text{cm}^2$ to $30\text{mA}/\text{cm}^2$, and obtained potential window was 1.5V . ASC displayed characteristic battery type GCD shape which was in continuity with the results pattern shown in CV graphs. GCD plots manifested good Coulombic efficiency, with high symmetry and slight IR drop. The IR drop increases with the increase in current density, this drop is useful to calculate ESR. Specific and volumetric capacities are expressed in Fig. 5.7(b), which were calculated using eq 5.4

and eq 5.6 respectively. Calculated values of specific capacities for ASC were ~190, 182, 173.3, 164.6, 154.23, 147.8, 143.6, 140.38, 138, 135.72, 129 and 124.9 mAh g⁻¹ at volumetric capacities of ~1.2, 1.12, 1.001, 0.95, 0.91, 0.88, 0.85, 0.83, 0.8, 0.78, 0.76 and 0.75 mAh cm⁻³ at current densities of 2, 3, 4, 6, 8, 10, 12, 15, 18, 20, 25 and 30 mA cm⁻², respectively. The lower values of capacities at high current densities are due to compromised ion mobility.

$$C_{vc} = \frac{2I \times \int V dt}{V_{vol}} \quad (5.7)$$

Figure 5.7 (a) GCD curves of ASC at various current densities (b) specific and volumetric capacities of ASC

Cyclic performance for ASC is shown in Fig. 5.8(a), with an inset of last ten successive GCD cycles of ASC out of 3000 cycles. ASC retained round 93.3% of its initial capacity, which is quite high value. The stability test was executed at current density of 30mA/cm² for 3000 successive GCD cycles. Energy (E,Wh kg⁻¹) and power densities (P,W kg⁻¹) were calculated using equations below 5.7 and 5.8 respectively.

$$E = \frac{I \times \int V dt}{m \times 3.6} \quad (5.8)$$

$$P = \frac{E}{t} \times 3600 \quad (5.9)$$

The mass load used to assemble ASC for positive MXene-CoS was ~3mg whereas for negative electrode the mass load was ~4.8mg. Despite the fact that mass load was not that high, the ASC has shown excellent electrochemical performance with high energy density as 40 Wh kg⁻¹ and power density as ~400 W kg⁻¹. The Ragone plot of as-prepared ASC is represented in Fig. 5.8(b), the energy density and power density recorded for this device is higher than MXene-CoS₂ (CCH) (H. Liu et al., 2020), CNT@Mn-MOF (6.9 Wh kg⁻¹ at 122W kg⁻¹) (Y. Zhang et al., 2015), Ni/Co MOF-rGO//AC (20.9 Wh kg⁻¹ at 800 W kg⁻¹) (S. Gao et al., 2018), CoMn MOF (30 Wh kg⁻¹ at 2285 W kg⁻¹) (Shinde et al., 2020) and Ni Co₂S₄ (28 Wh kg⁻¹ at 245 W kg⁻¹) (Y. Zhu et al., 2015), showing its superior performance.

Figure 5.8 (a) Cyclic stability of ASC (b) Ragone plot displaying energy and power densities

5.3 Electrochemical performance of MXene-FeCu MOF

Electrochemical performance of as prepared MXene-FeCu MOF electrode was also carried out in a three electrode configuration with Pt foil as counter electrode and a reference electrode. CV plots of MXene-FeCu MOF at varying scan rates from 5mV/S to 30mV/S are displayed in Fig. 5.9(a). CV plots manifested a couple of Faradic peaks, with prominent oxidation and reduction peaks. CV plots manifested typical battery type behavior with and high redox activity (Brousse et al., 2015). With varying scan

rate, excellent redox reversibility and synonymous shape in CV plots can be seen. Due to polarization effect and internal resistance of the materials a slight shift of oxidation peaks was observed towards higher potential whereas in reduction peaks the slight shift occurred towards low potential region (He et al., 2018). In a contiguous image in Fig. 5.9(b) a CV comparison of MXene-FeCu MOF and stand-alone FeCu MOF is shown. The scan rate kept for this comparison was 30mV/s. Possible Faradic reaction can be written as under.

Electrochemical performance of as prepared MXene-FeCu MOF was far more superior than stand-alone FeCu MOF. The functional groups attached to MXene help in enhancing surface redox reactions, moreover the intercalation between MXene sheets and cations (K^+) are the key reason for this performance enhancement. The chemical reaction can be written as below (Naguib, Mashtalir, et al., 2014).

Figure 5.9 (a) CV plots of as MXene-FeCu MOF (b) CV comparison of MXene-FeCu MOF and stand-alone FeCu MOF

In Fig.5.10(a) GCD plots of MXene-FeCu MOF at various current densities are shown. GCD tests were undertaken from current density value of 3mAcm^{-2} to 40mAcm^{-2} . MXene-FeCu MOF electrode manifested excellent slopy charging and discharging curves with excellent redox activity which is in continuity of CV results discussed

earlier. The maximum obtained values for discharging time and specific capacity were ~ 500 S and ~ 440 mA h cm^{-2} respectively at current density of 3 mA cm^{-2} .

Cyclic performance and stability of active electrode material are displayed in Fig. 5.10(b). As prepared MXene-FeCu MOF electrode underwent cyclic stability for 5000 successive GCD cycles at the current density of 15 mA cm^{-2} . The electrode retained 93% of its initial capacity after completing 5000 cycles. The last ten GCD cycles are shown in the inset of Fig. 5.10(b), clearly the shape and symmetry of the as prepared electrode was well maintained and kept well.

Figure 5.10 (a) GCD plots of MXene-FeCu MOF (b) cyclic stability of MXene-FeCu MOF

Since EIS tests help to understand the resistance of the material. Solution and charge transfer resistances are established with the help of EIS. In Fig. 5.11(a) Nyquist plots of MXene-FeCu MOF and stand-alone FeCu MOF are shown, with the inset of equivalent circuit. The charge transfer resistance R_{ct} for MXene-FeCu MOF was $\sim 0.9\Omega$ whereas for FeCu MOF the R_{ct} value was $\sim 1.2\Omega$ which is quite higher than MXene-FeCu MOF.

Fig. 5.11(b) displays the specific capacities (C_{SC} , mAhg^{-1}) and areal capacities (C_{AC} , mAhcm^{-2}) MXene-FeCu MOF. Specific and areal capacities were calculated using eq 5.4 and eq 5.5. Obtained values of specific capacities were $\sim 440, 410, 396, 387, 360, 342, 335, 318, 305, 290 \text{ mA h g}^{-1}$ at various current densities of 3, 5, 8, 10, 12, 15, 18, 20, 30 and 40 mA cm^{-2} . Whereas the areal capacities of MXene-FeCu MOF electrode at same current densities were $\sim 2.1, 1.97, 1.91, 1.90, 1.89, 1.81, 1.74, 1.52, 1.45$ and 1.39 mAh cm^{-2} .

Figure 5.11 (a) EIS plots of MXene-FeCu MOF and FeCu MOF (b) specific and areal capacities of MXene-FeCu MOF

5.4 Electrochemical performance of MXene-FeCu MOF/AC ASC

Electrochemical performance of MXene-FeCu MOF/AC ASC was designed and assembled in similar manner as we discussed earlier in section 5.2. In Fig. 5.12 CV graphs of ASC are displayed. CV plots at varying potential and constant scan rate 20 mVs^{-1} are expressed in Fig. 5.12(a). The potential range was kept from 0.6 to 1.5V so

that optimum potential window could be achieved. The reason implied here is to establish appropriate potential window with prominent oxidation and reduction peaks. It is obvious that from potential range 0.6 to 0.9V no significant CV shape could be developed. After reaching to potential 1V, ASC started developing shape, the characteristic shape was fully achieved at 1.5V.

CV graphs of ASC are displayed in Fig. 5.12(b), these tests were carried out at scan rate from 5 to 30mVs⁻¹ with potential 1.5V. ASC displayed characteristic battery-type CV pattern, the shape was well maintained and kept intact on the increment in scan rate. This indicate occurrence of excellent rate capability and superior Faradic reaction that are taking place between the electrodes (Bahaa et al., 2019).

Figure 5.12 (a) CV of ASC at constant scan rate with varying potential window (b) CV of ASC at varying scan rate

In Fig. 5.13 GCD plots along with specific and volumetric capacities are expressed. GCD plots of ASC are shown in Fig. 5.13(a), with the current densities ranging from 3mA/cm^2 to 30mA/cm^2 . ASC achieved operational potential of 1.4V for GCD plots. The charge discharge pattern revealed a typical battery type shape which is continuous

with CV results. Overall graph shape is symmetric, with slight IR drop which is associated to internal resistance of ASC. The shape and symmetry of GCD plots are the manifestation of Faradic Redox reactions that are occurring during every charging discharging cycle (Bahaa et al., 2019; H. Liu et al., 2020).

Specific capacity and volumetric capacity are the key aspects to declare the performance of SC device. In Fig. 5.13(b) specific and volumetric capacities of as prepared ASC are displayed. The obtained values of specific capacities are ~171, 157, 137, 114, 85, 70, 63, 55, 50 mA h g⁻¹ with volumetric capacities of ~0.76, 0.69, 0.60, 0.53, 0.39, 0.3, 0.2, 0.17 and 0.14 mA h cm⁻³ at current densities of 3, 5, 8, 10, 12, 15, 18, 20 and 30 mAcm⁻². Specific (C_{sc}) and (C_{vc}) volumetric capacities were calculated using eq 5.4 and 5.6.

Figure 5.13 (a) GCD plots of ASC at varying current density (b) specific and volumetric capacities of ASC

Cyclic stability and ragone plots of ASC are shown in Fig. 5.14. Cyclic stability is shown in Fig. 5.14(a) with cyclic performance represented in the inset. ASC maintained 89% of its initial capacity at current density 15mA cm^{-2} after 10,000 successive GCD cycles. Last ten GCD cycles are expressed in the inset and with a well maintained shape and pattern. In a contiguous image, of Fig. 5.14(b) energy density (Wh kg^{-1}) and power density (W kg^{-1}) are expressed, both were calculated using eq 5.7 and 5.8. The assembled ASC device manifested excellent value of energy density

~33.3Wh kg⁻¹ followed by moderate power density ~503W kg⁻¹ respectively. These values are compared with other contemporary MOF and 2D materials studies such as as rGO/CMOF(17.2Wh kg⁻¹, 250Wkg⁻¹) (Wen et al., 2016) , Cu MOF@C (18.3Wh kg⁻¹, 350Wkg⁻¹) (Z.-X. Li et al., 2019), Zn MOF (10.86 Wh kg⁻¹, 225Wkg⁻¹) (Salunkhe et al., 2014), CNT@Mn MOF (6.9Wh kg⁻¹ at 122W kg⁻¹) (Y. Zhang et al., 2015), Bi-MXene (15.2Wh kg⁻¹, 564Wkg⁻¹) (Xia et al., 2018) and MnO₂-MXene (12.25Wh kg⁻¹, 700Wkg⁻¹) (Rakhi et al., 2016).

Figure 5.14 (a) Cyclic stability of ASC (b) Ragone plot

5.5 Electrochemical performance of MXene-Fe MOF

Electrochemical evaluation for MXene-Fe MOF electrode was carried out in a three electrode configuration. CV plots of as prepared MXene-Fe MOF are shown in Fig. 5.15(a) at varying scan rate from 5mV/S to 30mV/S in the presence of 2M KOH electrolyte. A couple of Faradic peaks is observed with characteristic oxidation and reduction peaks, CV plots have shown a characteristic battery type behavior (Brousse et al., 2015). Excellent redox reversibility and shape symmetry of CV curves proves the success of achieving high quality of electrode material. Slight peak shift at higher scan rates could be attributed to polarization effect and internal resistance of the as prepared electrode (He et al., 2018). In Fig. 5.15(b) a CV comparison between stand-alone Fe MOF and MXene-Fe MOF is shown at scan rate of 5mV/s. MXene-Fe MOF exhibited excellent current response as compared to stand-alone Fe MOF proving improved electrochemical performance of as prepared composite. The potential Faradic reaction can be reported as below.

Enhanced electrochemical performance of MXene-Fe MOF is attributed to intercalation between MXene flakes cations (K^+), in addition to that MXene sheets possess surface functional groups that contribute to surface redox reactions. The possible chemical reaction can be written as under.

Figure 5.15 (a) CV plots of MXene-Fe MOF (b) CV comparison of MXene-Fe MOF and stand-alone Fe-MOF

GCD plots of as prepared MXene-Fe MOF at various current densities from $3\text{mA}/\text{cm}^2$ to $40\text{mA}/\text{cm}^2$ are shown in Fig. 5.16(a). Potential curves with smooth and absolute shape symmetry can be seen. As prepared electrode manifested typical characteristic battery-type GCD curves with high redox activity, which complements the CV results. The composite achieved potential value of 0.5V , with the max discharging time ~ 550 S at current density of $3\text{mA}/\text{cm}^2$. For further evaluation, as prepared electrode was tested for its cyclic performance. Cyclic performance of MXene-Fe MOF is displayed in Fig. 5.16(b) the electrode was tested for ten thousand consecutive GCD cycles, at constant current density which is $15\text{mA}/\text{cm}^2$. At the conclusion of ten thousand cycles,

the electrode retained ~91% of its initial capacity. The shape of GCD cycles almost remained symmetrical throughout the cycling process. The inset in Fig. 5.16(b) shows last GCD cycles of cyclic performance of prepared electrode.

Figure 5.16 (a) GCD plots of MXene-Fe MOF (b) cyclic stability performance of MXene-Fe MOF

EIS studies are carried out to establish charge transfer resistance and solution resistance of electrode. In Fig. 5.17(a) Nyquist plots of stand-alone Fe MOF and MXene-Fe MOF are displayed. EIS plots work in two frequency regions, low frequency region and high frequency region. Charge transfer resistance R_{ct} for MXene-Fe MOF was $\sim 0.36\Omega$, whereas solution resistance R_s turned out $\sim 1.3\Omega$, meanwhile

R_{ct} and R_s values for stand-alone Fe MOF turned out to be $\sim 0.6\Omega$ and $\sim 2.3\Omega$ respectively. The formation of semicircle at high frequency region indicates contact resistance and capacitance between active material and substrate which is NF in our case. The diameter size of the semi-circle tells contact resistance and capacitance values of electrode, the greater the diameter larger the values. Therefore, it is concluded that overall resistance found in MXene-Fe MOF was lesser than stand-alone Fe MOF. The low R_s values of MXene-Fe MOF proves its capacitive as well as conductive nature. The ESR circuit is shown in the inset in Fig. 5.17(a)

Fig. 5.17(b) displayed specific and areal capacities of MXene-Fe MOF electrode; the obtained values of specific capacities are $\sim 414, 398, 384, 380, 374, 360, 344, 330, 324, 320$ mA h g^{-1} at varying current densities of 3, 5, 8, 10, 12, 15, 18, 20, 30 and 40 mA cm^{-2} . Meanwhile corresponding areal capacities are $\sim 1.8, 1.7, 1.65, 1.62, 1.59, 1.55, 1.48, 1.47, 1.45, 1.43$ mA h/ cm^2 . These excellent values of specific and areal capacities manifest superior electrochemical performance of as prepared MXene-Fe MOF and it also lays the ground of this work to be further investigated in a two electrode device to evaluate its performance in future perspective.

Figure 5.17 (a) EIS plots of stand-alone Fe MOF and MXene-Fe MOF (b) Specific and areal capacities of MXene-Fe MOF

5.6 Electrochemical performance of MXene-Fe MOF/AC ASC

In previous section electrochemical performance evaluation of MXene-Fe MOF electrode is thoroughly discussed. For further evaluation and in-depth investigation of electrode behavior in two electrode charge devices, an ASC SC device was assembled. The device assembly remained same as we discussed in section 5.2 and 5.4. AC was used as negative electrode and as prepared MXene-Fe MOF as positive electrode. The performance evaluation started from carrying out CV of the device.

CV graphs at constant scan rate and varying potential window are expressed in Fig. 5.18(a). Here the device was tested at varying potential window which was 0.6V to 1.6V, at a constant scan rate of 25mV/S. The purpose of varying the potential window was to establish a particular operating range of the device where prominent oxidation and reduction peaks are observed. So, the same range can be fixed for the upcoming CV performance evaluation. As it is obvious for 0.6V to 1V no obvious CV pattern with characteristic oxidation and reduction peaks is observed. After 1V the device started manifesting oxidation peaks followed by reduction peaks until 1.6V. After reaching to the potential window range of 1.6V the device showed clear oxidation and reduction peaks which is signature CV pattern for SC devices. Hence 1.6V of potential range was fixed for the device CV. In Fig.5.18(b) CV of assembled device is shown, at varying scan rate of 5mV/S to 30mV/S at potential window of 1.6V. CV of ASC displayed battery-type pattern, which is in continuity of the electrochemical performance of MXene-Fe MOF electrode. The shape of oxidation and reduction peaks remained well maintained at the increment of scan rate. The shape retention of CV is indication of superior reversible Faradic reaction occurring in the device (Bahaa et al., 2019).

Figure 5.18 (a) CV of ASC at constant rate and varying potential window (b) CV of ASC at varying scan rate

GCD plots as well as specific and volumetric capacities of ASC are shown in Fig. 5.19.

The ASC was tested at varying current densities from $3\text{mA}/\text{cm}^2$ to $30\text{mA}/\text{cm}^2$ for GCD studies as shown in Fig. 5.19(a). Likewise, CV studies, potential window achieved here was 1.6V , with typical battery-type behavior. The charge discharge shape of

remained completely symmetric with negligible IR drop which is due to internal resistance of the device. Faradic redox reactions were occurring during charge discharge cycles which is evident from the shape symmetry of the GCD plots (Bahaa et al., 2019; H. Liu et al., 2020).

Capacities whether it is specific capacity or volumetric capacity is of prime importance in evaluating any energy storage device. The capacities were calculated using eq 5.4 and 5.6 for specific and volumetric capacity respectively and shown in Fig. 5.19(b). The obtained values of specific capacity are ~204, 180, 170, 118, 113, 105, 99.3, 98.7, 97.6 mA h g⁻¹ at the current density values of 3, 5, 8, 10, 12, 15, 20, 25, 30 mAcm⁻². The corresponding volumetric capacities were calculated as ~1.9, 1.7, 1.39, 0.9, 0.85, 0.81, 0.78, 0.75, 0.69 mAh/cm³.

Figure 5.19 (a) GCD plots of ASC (b) Specific and volumetric capacities of ASC

Cyclic performance of ASC and Ragone plot expressing energy and power densities in comparison with other contemporary studies is shown in Fig. 5.20. Assembled ASC device was tested for ten thousand successive GCD cycles, to evaluate its cyclic performance and the results are shown in Fig. 5.20(a). ASC retained ~89.9% of its initial capacity after completing the stability test of ten thousand cycles. It is also evident from the inset in Fig. 5.20(a) showing first ten and last ten GCD cycles, that the ASC maintained its potential and shape symmetry throughout the process and no significant change is observed. Energy and power densities have key importance in establishing the quality and class of any energy storage device. The max obtained value of energy density of ASC was ~51.2Wh/kg whereas the power density was ~750W/kg.

These values were recorded at current density of $3\text{mA}/\text{cm}^2$. These values were compared with other contemporary studies and remained higher in values. Ragone plot shown in Fig. 5.20(b) displays these studies as NiCo-LDH@NCF//AC (41.5 Wh/kg and 750 W/kg) (Y. Liu, Wang, et al., 2020), CoNi-LDH//AC (46.3 Wh/kg, 102.3 W/kg) (L. Xie et al., 2016), NiS₂/ZnS//AC (28.0 Wh/kg and 748 W/kg) (G.-C. Li et al., 2016), MnO₂/HCSs//HCSs (26.8 Wh/kg and 170 W/kg) (G. Wang et al., 2022), AC//H-NiCoSe₂ (35 Wh/kg and 188W/kg) (Hou et al., 2018), N-PMCN (32.6 Wh/kg and 415 W/kg) (H. Peng et al., 2017), AC/MXene (17 Wh/kg and 40W/kg) (L. Yu et al., 2018).

Figure 5.20 (a) Cyclic performance of ASC (b) Ragone plot showing energy and power density

Realtime assembly of three electrodes and two electrodes ASC device is displayed in Fig. 5.21. Here in Fig. 5.21(a) set of three electrodes, working, counter and reference electrodes is shown connected to biologic workstation. In contiguous image Fig. 5.21(b) two electrodes ASC device assembly is shown, here AC is coupled with either of the prepared active electrode.

Figure 5.21 (a) Three electrode configuration (b) Two electrode ASC device assembly

Discussion

As aims and objectives are stated in chapter 1, keeping them in view it is highly encouraging that almost all of the aims have been actualized and all the objectives have been successfully achieved. After thorough study, a novel and promising composite material was designed. Not only that all the structural and chemical limitations were thoroughly discussed but this study provided a possible solution to those limitations. Three different MOFs and at one instance their derivatives were made composites with MXene, in a clean synthesis method. As mentioned earlier that three sets were prepared and all of them were studied for EC testing to prove the authenticity and reliability of this study. The synthesis method was kept simple and least hazardous materials were used with few exceptions. All the obtained materials underwent a variety of chemical and structural characterizations, for example morphological

studies, crystal structure, chemical bonding and chemical composition was thoroughly studied.

MXene-MOF synergized electrodes were successfully obtained, in a free standing material growth over NF. No binder and additive were used to grow the materials over the substrate. All the electrodes were electrochemically tested and displayed battery type behavior. The as prepared electrodes manifested excellent values of areal, volumetric, and specific capacities. Moreover, high values of energy and power densities were recorded making them promising candidate for future work in energy storage specifically in the field of SCs. Another glaring aspect of this work is that all the electrodes and assembled ASC devices held excellent cyclic stability, a series of individual tests of successive GCD cycles on each electrode proved that the materials and as prepared electrodes were stable and had retained maximum of their initial capacities.

These results were compared with other similar contemporary studies, Ragone plots depicting energy density and power density were drawn. Since, the values of energy and power densities are important to differentiate between the performance and classification of storage devices. As discussed earlier that EDLCs suffer from low energy density while having high power density whereas Pseudocapacitors have both high energy and power density but suffer from low cyclic stability. Moreover, it is also important that a hybrid system that could bridge the gaps between SCs and batteries becomes highly important to be actualize. Therefore, our results have the potential to become that bridge. The high values of energy density and power density while maintaining excellent stability are the key gains from this work.

Chapter 6. Conclusion

Overall impression of the study

The summary of this work can be expressed in several ways, such as Novelty, performance, and stability. The aim of growing MXene-MOF composites in a binder free growth scheme was achieved successfully. A series of three composite electrodes was successfully developed. All the electrodes and devices manifested superior electrochemical activity. High values of energy and power densities were achieved, having a great potential to bridge the gap between SCs and batteries. To the best of our knowledge for the first time 2D MXene, MOFs and derived structures have been successfully synthesized and used in supercapacitors. Three sets of each electrode have been prepared and evaluated to see the performance. No significant variation and performance deviation was observed, and very time performance was same proving the authenticity and viability of the prepared electrodes. The composite helped in treating the conventional defects of MOFs such as conductivity as well as structural limitations of MXene like crushing and restacking. The synthesized materials were directly grown on 3d porous Ni foam in hydrothermal technique without any additive or binder. The prepared electrodes MXene-CoS, MXene-FeCu MOF and MXene-Fe MOF displayed excellent specific capacities $\sim 447 \text{ mAh g}^{-1}$, $\sim 440 \text{ mAh g}^{-1}$, and $\sim 414 \text{ mAh g}^{-1}$ respectively at current density of 3 mA cm^{-2} . Meanwhile MXene-CoS, MXene-FeCu MOF, and MXene-Fe MOF displayed excellent capacity retention of 94%, 93.3%, and 91% respectively. Moreover, the as prepared asymmetric supercapacitor device, showcased excellent values of energy and power densities. MXene-CoS/AC device gave 40 Wh kg^{-1} of energy density and $\sim 400 \text{ W kg}^{-1}$ of power density. Whereas MXene-FeCu MOF /AC displayed energy density $\sim 33.3 \text{ Wh kg}^{-1}$ and

power density $\sim 503 \text{ W kg}^{-1}$. MXene-Fe MOF /AC manifested energy density of $\sim 51.2 \text{ Wh/kg}$ whereas the power density was $\sim 750 \text{ W/kg}$. Electrochemical evaluation of devices was compared to other contemporary similar studies and proven far superior. Superior electrochemical performance of these devices verifies the authenticity, viability and reliability of the overall experiments and synthesis procedure of MXene-MOF composite. A performance -comparison of this work with other contemporary studies is demonstrated in the table 6-1 below. In this table the comparison is drawn on three basic categories, showing capacity retention energy densities and power densities. The energy and power densities proven to be superior, when compared with other similar studies. Moreover, another important aspect such as capacity retention is also compared proving the excellent and high values of this work over contemporary studies.

Electrode Material	Energy Density Wh/Kg	Power density W/kg	Retention rate	Ref
MXene-CoS	~40	~400	93.3%	This work
MXene-FeCu MOF	~33.3	~503	89%	This work
MXene-Fe MOF	~51.2	~750	89.9%	This work
NiCo ₂ S ₄	~28	~245	91.7%	(Y. Zhu et al., 2015)
MX-HGH	~ 15.4	~ 288.7	83.2%	(Z. Zhu et al., 2022)
AC/MXene	~ 17	~ 40	57.9%	(L. Yu et al., 2018)
CuCo ₂ Se ₄ //AC	~ 9.45	~850	88%	(Tavakoli et al., 2019)
MxeneCoS ₂	28.8	~800	98%	(H. Liu et al., 2020)
NiCoFe@MXene	32.5	~895	80%	(J. Chen et al., 2021)
NiS@MXene	20	~500	71.4%	(Y. Luo et al., 2020)

Table 6-1 Table shows a detailed performance comparison of this work with other contemporary studies

A promising, cost effective, ecofriendly and scalable design is proposed to fabricate and design nanostructured energy storage and conversion devices for modern electronics. The fabrication of these 2D MXene-MOF composites and derived structures is very new in its model, we hope that future work in developing a diverse range of composite formation will bring more promising results that could be cost effective, ecofriendly, and scalable for industrial use.

For any SC along with electrochemical performance sustainability and durability is of great importance. The electrodes prepared in this study, have been tested for their cyclic stability over thousands of cycles proving them sustainable and durable under certain current densities. Since all the electrodes were tested at ambient conditions, therefore it is also important to test them at varying temperature conditions. This will

open a new window for future work, to see the performance of these electrodes at high temperatures or low temperatures. Moreover, if such cells are prepared that could be tested under stress or shock will further reveal about the mechanical strength of the potential cells from these electrodes.

Limitations and risks of this study

Keeping in view the environmental risks, development of ecofriendly materials with minimum toxicity are highly demanded. One of the key factors while conceptualizing this work was to keep the synthesis method clean with limited use of hazardous materials. However, some toxic materials were employed such as HF, but it was unavoidable to achieve exfoliation of MXene sheets. If etchants with minimum toxicity are used, they could help in achieving more greener and cleaner synthesis methods but that was beyond the objective of this work.

Future work

Future work is highly imperative for any novel work, sustainability, ecofriendly and cost effective are the foundations for any work to be taken into consideration for future work. The presented studies, have great potential to be explored further in future. As discussed earlier that there are thousands of MOFs structures that have been identified so far, and there are many such MOFs that have been studied in various energy storage applications. This study opens the avenue of exploring other MOFs and MXene synergized composites for energy storage applications primarily in SCs.

Another very important aspect is the growth amount of active material on the substrate. If the growth is not optimized the electrodes can get prompt deterioration of mass load during EC tests. If the mass load is managed more properly, and the growth of active material is increased, the overall performance of the future electrodes developed using

this method can be more superior. It is not only mass load that is crucial, but optimum ratio of mass load and keeping it intact with the substrate is also very important. Therefore, the mass load and binding strength between mass load and substrate should be optimized properly in order to obtain superior EC performance. Therefore, it is believed that if this area is further explored it can bring interesting findings that will be helpful for the future research.

Any lab scale project no matter how efficient it is, has to be in compliance with the cost effectivity if it is to be scaled up. In this project beside using simple method to prepare electrodes, experimental cost was also considered. All the used materials such as precursor salts, MAX phase and organic linkers were low cost and readily available. This shows that if certain shortcomings that are mentioned earlier are addressed aptly this work has the potential to be expanded commercially.

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